

Optimal Stateless Model Checking for Causal Consistency

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Abstract. We present a framework for efficient stateless model checking (SMC) of concurrent programs under three prominent models of causal consistency, CCv, CM, CC. Our approach is based on exploring traces under the program order *po* and the reads from *rf* relations. Our SMC algorithm is provably optimal in the sense that it explores each *po* and *rf* relation exactly once. We have implemented our framework in a tool called CONSCHECKER. Experiments show that CONSCHECKER performs well in detecting anomalies in classical distributed databases benchmarks.

1 Introduction

Traditionally, distributed shared memories ensure that all processes in the system agree on a common order of all operations on memory. Such guarantees are provided by sequential consistency (SC) [33], and by linearizable memory [26]. However, providing these consistency guarantees entails access latencies, making them inefficient for large systems. There is a tradeoff in providing strong consistency guarantees while ensuring low latency and this presents significant efficiency challenges. There is a large body of work which suggests that a systematic weakening of memory consistency can reduce the costs of providing consistency. Weakened consistency guarantees admit more concurrent behaviours than SC or linearizability. To this end, Lamport [32] proposed *causal consistency* which provides an ordering among events in a distributed system in which processes communicate via message passing. This has been adapted [6] to a setting of reads and writes in a shared memory environment. In this setting, the return values of reads must be consistent with causally related reads and writes. As causality only orders events partially, the reading processes can disagree on the relative ordering of concurrent writes. This makes concurrent writer processes independent, reducing the costs of synchronization.

Several efforts have been made to formalize causal consistency [15], [25], [39] [40], [6], [14], [9], [7], [38] and there are many implementations [8], [20], [21] satisfying this criterion as opposed to strong consistency (linearizability).

While strong consistency makes it easier to program than weak ones, they require costly implementations. Weak memories may be easier to implement, but much harder to program. An acceptable medium which has emerged over the years are three important notions in causal consistency, respectively *causal consistency* (CC) [14], [25], *causal convergence* (CCv) [15], [39], [14], [25] and *causal memory* (CM) [6], [39], [14], [25].

The focus of this paper is the verification of shared memory programs under causal consistency. We consider the three variants mentioned above. We propose a stateless model checking (SMC) framework that covers all three variants. SMC is a successful technique for finding concurrency bugs [23]. For a terminating program, SMC systematically explores all process schedulings that are possible during runs of the program. The number of possible schedulings grows exponentially with the execution length in SMC. To counter this and reduce the number of explored executions, the technique of *partial order reduction* [17,22] has been proposed. This has been adapted to SMC as DPOR (dynamic partial order reduction). DPOR was first developed for concurrent programs under SC [1,41]. Recent years have seen DPOR adapted to language induced weak memory models [28,37],[4], as well as hardware-induced relaxed memory models [2,46]. To the best of our knowledge, DPOR algorithms have not been developed for causal consistency models. The goal of this paper is to fill this gap.

DPOR is based on the observation that two executions are equivalent if they induce the same ordering between conflicting events, and hence it is sufficient to consider one such execution from each equivalence class. Under sequential consistency, these equivalence classes are called *Mazurkiewicz* traces [34], while for relaxed memory models, the generalization of these are called *Shasha-Snir* traces [42]. A Shasha-Snir trace characterizes an execution of a concurrent program by the relations (1) *po* program order, which totally orders events of each process, (2), *rf* reads from, which connects each read with the write it reads from, (3) *co* coherence order, which totally orders writes to the same shared variable. DPOR can be optimized further by observing that the assertions to be verified at the end of an execution does not depend on the coherence order of shared variables, and hence it suffices to consider traces over *po – rf*. Based on this observation, the DPOR algorithms for programs under the release-acquire semantics (RA) and SC [4], [3] explores traces with *po*, *rf* and *co* where the *co* edges are added on the fly. The equivalence classes are considered wrt *po – rf*, reducing the number of distinct traces to be analyzed.

Contributions. We propose a DPOR based SMC algorithm for all three consistency models CC, CCv, CM which explores systematically, all the distinct *po-rf* traces covering all possible executions of the program. We develop a uniform algorithm for all three models which is sound and complete : that is, all traces explored are consistent wrt the model $X \in \{\text{CC}, \text{CCv}, \text{CM}\}$ under consideration, and all such consistent traces are explored. Moreover, our algorithm is optimal in the sense that, each consistent *po-rf* trace is explored exactly once. One of the key challenges during the trace exploration is to maintain the consistency of the traces wrt the model under consideration. We tackle this by defining a *trace se-*

mantics which ensures that the traces generated in each step only contain edges which will be present in any consistent trace. We implement our algorithms in a tool CONSCHECKER which is, to the best of our knowledge, the first of its kind to perform SMC on the three prominent causal consistency models CC , CCv , CM . CONSCHECKER checks for assertion violation of programs under CC , CCv , CM . We evaluate the correctness of our tool on CC , CCv , CM by simulating these models on the memory model simulator Herd [7] and validating our outcomes with theirs. Then we proceed with experimental evaluation on a wide range of benchmarks from distributed databases. We showed that (i) CONSCHECKER correctly detects known consistency bugs [12], [13], [11] and [10] under CCv , CM , CC , (ii) CONSCHECKER correctly detects known assertion violations in applications [19], [27], [11], [36]. We also did a stress test of CONSCHECKER on some SV-COMP benchmarks and parameterized benchmarks which resulted in a large number (6 million) of traces.

Related Work. SMC has been implemented in many tools CHESS [35], Conqueror [16], VeriSoft [24], NIDHUGG [2], CDSChecker [37], RCMC[28], GenMC [30], rInspect [46] and Tracer [4]. While most of these work with either Mazurkewicz traces or *po* – *rf* traces, [5] proposes a RVF-SMC algorithm where the value read is used to decide equivalence of two runs.

In recent years, there has been much interest in DPOR algorithms : [3] for SC, [30] for the release acquire semantics, [43] for C/C++, and [29] for TSO, PSO and RC11. It is known that CC is weaker than RA, CCv is stronger than RA while CM is incomparable with RA [31]. In conclusion, all the above memory models are different from CC , CCv , CM . Hence we cannot reuse any of the existing DPOR algorithms.

Recent work on causal consistency [14] studies the complexity of checking whether one execution (all executions) of a program under CC , CCv , CM is consistent. They show that checking if an execution is consistent is NP-completeness, while the question of checking if all executions are consistent is undecidable. [10], [11] explore the robustness wrt SC, of transactional programs under CC , CCv , CM . However, none of these papers propose a DPOR algorithm for CC , CCv , CM .

2 Preliminaries

Programs We consider a program \mathcal{P} consisting of a finite set \mathcal{T} of *threads* (*processes*) that share a finite set \mathbb{X} of (*shared*) *variables*, ranging over a domain \mathbb{V} of *values* that includes a special value 0.

A process has a finite set of local registers that store values from \mathbb{V} . Each process runs a deterministic code, built in a standard way from expressions and atomic commands, using standard control flow constructs (sequential composition, selection, and bounded loop constructs). Throughout the paper, we use x, y for shared variables, $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}$ for registers, and e for expressions. *Global statements* are either writes $x := e$ to a shared variable, or reads $\mathbf{a} := x$ from a shared variable. *Local statements* only access and affect the local state of the process and include assignments $\mathbf{a} := e$ to registers, and conditional control flow constructs.

Note that expressions do not contain shared variables, implying that a statement accesses at most one shared variable.

The local state of a process $proc \in \mathcal{T}$ is defined by its program counter and the contents of its registers. A *configuration* of \mathcal{P} is made up of the local states of all the processes. The values of the shared variables are not part of a configuration. A program execution is a sequence of transitions between configurations, starting with the initial configuration γ^{init} . Each transition corresponds to one process performing a local or global statement. A transition between two configurations γ and γ' is of form $\gamma \xrightarrow{\ell} \gamma'$, where the label ℓ describes the interaction with shared variables. The label ℓ is one of three forms: (i) $\langle proc, \varepsilon \rangle$, indicating a local statement performed by thread $proc$, which updates only the local state of $proc$, (ii) $\langle proc, \text{wt}, x, v \rangle$, indicating a write of the value v to the variable x by the thread $proc$, which also updates the program counter of $proc$, and (iii) $\langle proc, \text{rd}, x, v \rangle$ indicating a read of v from x by the thread $proc$ into some register, while also updating the program counter of $proc$. There is no constraint on the values that are used in transitions corresponding to read statements. This will allow some illegal program behaviors, which is sorted by associating runs with so-called *traces*, which represent how reads obtain their values from writes. A causal consistency model $X \in \{\text{CC}, \text{CCv}, \text{CM}\}$ is formulated by imposing restrictions on traces, thereby also restricting the possible runs that are associated with them.

Since local statements are not visible to other threads, we will not represent them explicitly in the transition relation considered in our DPOR algorithm. Instead, we let each transition represent the combined effect of some finite sequence of local statements by a process followed by a global statement by the same process. For configurations γ and γ' and a label ℓ which is either of the form $\langle proc, \text{wt}, x, v \rangle$ or of the form $\langle proc, \text{rd}, x, v \rangle$, we let $\gamma \xrightarrow{\ell} \gamma'$ denote that we can reach γ' from γ by performing a sequence of transitions labeled with $\langle proc, \varepsilon \rangle$ followed by a transition labeled with ℓ . Defining the relation \rightarrow in this manner ensures that we take the effect of local statements into account, while avoiding consideration of interleavings of local statements of different threads in the analysis.

We use $\gamma \rightarrow \gamma'$ to denote that $\gamma \xrightarrow{\ell} \gamma'$ for some ℓ and define $\text{succ}(\gamma) := \{\gamma' \mid \gamma \rightarrow \gamma'\}$, i.e., it is the set of successors of γ wrt. \rightarrow . A configuration γ is said to be *terminal* if $\text{succ}(\gamma) = \emptyset$, i.e., no thread can execute a global statement from γ . A *run* ρ from γ is a sequence $\gamma_0 \xrightarrow{\ell_1} \gamma_1 \xrightarrow{\ell_2} \dots \xrightarrow{\ell_n} \gamma_n$ such that $\gamma_0 = \gamma$. We say that ρ is *terminated* if γ_n is terminal. We let $\text{Runs}(\gamma)$ denote the set of runs from γ .

Events. An event corresponds to a particular execution of a statement in a run of \mathcal{P} . A *write event* ev is given by $(id, proc, \text{wt}(x, v))$ where $id \in \mathbb{N}$ is the identifier of the event, $proc$ is the process containing the event, $x \in \mathbb{X}$ is a variable, and $v \in \mathbb{V}$ is a value. This event corresponds to a process writing the value v to variable x . Likewise, a *read event* ev is given by $(id, proc, \text{rd}(x))$ where $x \in \mathbb{X}$. This event corresponds to a process reading some value to x . The read event ev does not specify the particular value it reads; this value will be defined in a trace by specifying a write event from which ev fetches its value. For each

variable $x \in \mathbb{X}$, we assume a special write event $\text{init}_x = \text{wt}(x, 0)$ called the *initializer* event for x . This event is not performed by any of the processes in \mathcal{T} , and writes the value 0 to x . We define $\mathbf{E}_{\text{init}} := \{\text{init}_x \mid x \in \mathbb{X}\}$ as the set of initializer events. If \mathbf{E} is a set of events, we define subsets of \mathbf{E} characterized by particular attributes of its events. For instance, for a variable x , we let $\mathbf{E}^{\text{wt},x}$ denote $\{ev \in \mathbf{E} \mid ev.type = \text{wt} \wedge ev.var = x\}$.

Traces. A *trace* τ is a tuple $\langle \mathbf{E}, \text{po}, \text{rf} \rangle$, where \mathbf{E} is a set of *events* which includes the set \mathbf{E}_{init} of initializer events, and po (program order), rf (read-from) are binary relations on \mathbf{E} that satisfy:

- $ev \text{ po } ev'$ if $\text{process}(ev) = \text{process}(ev')$ and $ev.id < ev'.id$. po totally orders the events of each individual process.
- $ev \text{ rf } ev'$ if ev is a write event and ev' is a read event on the same variable, which obtains its value from ev .

We can view $\tau = \langle \mathbf{E}, \text{po}, \text{rf} \rangle$ as a graph whose nodes are \mathbf{E} and whose edges are defined by the relations po, rf . po depicted by red solid edges captures the order in each process while rf edges are depicted as solid blue edges. We define the *empty trace* $\tau_\emptyset := \langle \mathbf{E}_{\text{init}}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle$, i.e., it contains only the initializer events, and all the relations are empty.

We define when a trace can be associated with a run. Consider a run ρ of form $\gamma_0 \xrightarrow{\ell_1} \dots \xrightarrow{\ell_n} \gamma_n$, where $\ell_i = \langle \text{proc}_i, \text{t}_i, x_i, v_i \rangle$, and let $\tau = \langle \mathbf{E}, \text{po}, \text{rf} \rangle$ be a trace. We write $\rho \models \tau$ to denote that the following conditions are satisfied: (i) $\mathbf{E} = \{ev_1, \dots, ev_n\}$, i.e., each event corresponds exactly to one label in ρ . (ii) If $\ell_i = \langle \text{proc}_i, \text{wt}, x_i, v_i \rangle$, then $ev_i = \langle id_i, \text{proc}_i, \text{wt}, x_i, v_i \rangle$, and if $\ell_i = \langle \text{proc}_i, \text{rd}, x_i, v_i \rangle$, then $ev_i = \langle id_i, \text{proc}_i, \text{rd}, x_i \rangle$. An event and its label do the same (write or read) on identical variables, and for writes, they also agree on the written value. (iii) $id_i = |\{j \mid (1 \leq j \leq i) \wedge (\text{proc}_j = \text{proc}_i)\}|$. $ev.id$ shows how it is ordered relative to the other events of $\text{process}(ev)$. (iv) if $ev_i \text{ rf } ev_j$ then $x_i = x_j$ and $v_i = v_j$. (v) if $\text{init}_x \text{ rf } ev_i$ then $v_i = 0$, i.e., ev_i reads the initial value of x which is 0.

3 Causally Consistent Models

We study three variants [14] of causal consistency : CC , CCv and CM . To define the three models formally, we introduce a function that, for each model, extends a given trace uniquely by a set of new edges. Then we define the model by requiring that the extended trace does not contain any cycles. A run of the program satisfies a consistency model X if its associated extended trace has no cycles.

Let CO , called *causality order* represent $(\text{po} \cup \text{rf})^+$. Two events e_1, e_2 are *causally related* if either $e_1 \text{ CO } e_2$ or $e_2 \text{ CO } e_1$.

Causal Consistency CC. We start presenting the weakest notion of causal consistency, CC [25], [6]. First we give an intuitive description of CC . In CC , events which are not causally related can be executed in different orders in different processes; moreover decisions made about these orders can be revised by each process. To illustrate, consider the program Fig.1(b). The write events $\text{wt}(x, 1), \text{wt}(x, 2)$ are not causally related and hence can be ordered in any way.

Fig. 1. Programs showing the differences between consistency models. The $\triangleright v$ denotes the expected return value of the read event.

Fig. 2. solid red, blue edges are po, rf , $wt(x, v)$ and $rd(x)$ are write, read events.

Note that p_b first orders $x := 1$ after $x := 2$ and reads 1 into a ; it then revises this order, and orders $x := 2$ after $x := 1$ and reads 2 into b .

A trace τ does not violate CC as long as there is a causality order which explains the return value of each read event.

To capture traces violating CC , we define a relation OW (for overwrite) on writes to the same variable. For any two writes w_1, w_2 and a read r on a same variable, if $w_1 CO w_2 CO r$, and $w_1 rf r$, then $w_2 OW w_1$. This says that r reads the overwritten write w_1 , resulting in a $CO \cup OW$ cycle. We refer to $CO \cup OW$ cycles as $CCcycle$. We define a function $extend_{CC}(\tau)$ which extends a trace $\tau = \langle E, po, rf \rangle$ by adding all possible OW edges between write events on the same variable. For a trace $\tau = \langle E, po, rf \rangle$, we say that $\tau \models CC$ iff $extend_{CC}(\tau)$ does not have a $CCcycle$.

Examples. Program Fig. 1(a) is not CC since there is no causality order which explains the return values of the read events. If we consider any trace (Fig. 2) of the program Fig.1(a), we find that $wt(y, 1) rf r$ where $r = rd(y)$, $wt(x, 1) po wt(y, 1)$, $r po wt(x, 2)$. Then we get $wt(x, 1) CO wt(x, 2)$, $wt(x, 2) CO r'$ where $r' = rd(x)$ and $wt(x, 1) rf r'$ giving $wt(x, 2) OW wt(x, 1)$ witnessing $CCcycle$.

Causal Convergence CCv . Under CCv , we need a total order on all write events per variable. This order, called *arbitration order*, is an abstraction of how conflicts are resolved by all processes to agree upon one ordering among events which are not causally related. Thus, unlike CC , a process cannot revise its ordering of the events which are not causally related, and all processes must follow one ordering. This makes it stronger than CC .

To enforce a total order between all writes, we use a new relation CF called conflict relation on all write events per variable. For all variables $x \in \mathcal{V}$, and writes w_1, w_2 on x and a read $r = rd(x)$, if $w_1 CO r$, and $w_2 rf r$ then $w_1 CF w_2$.

We define a function $\text{extend}_{\text{CCv}}(\tau)$ which extends a trace $\tau = \langle E, \text{po}, \text{rf} \rangle$ by adding all possible **OW**, **CF** edges between write events on the same variable. Traces violating **CCv** exhibit a $\text{CO} \cup \text{CF} \cup \text{OW}$ cycle in $\text{extend}_{\text{CCv}}(\tau)$, which we refer to as **CCv** cycle. We say that $\tau \models \text{CCv}$ iff $\text{extend}_{\text{CCv}}(\tau)$ does not contain a **CCv** cycle.

Examples. For the program Fig.1(b) and any trace τ , $\text{extend}_{\text{CCv}}(\tau)$ has a **CCv** cycle (see Fig.2) since in any trace, we have $w_1 = \text{wt}(x, 1) \text{ CO } r_2$ where $r_2 = \text{rd}(x)$ and $w_2 \text{ rf } r_2$ for $w_2 = \text{wt}(x, 2)$ giving $w_1 \text{ CF } w_2$. We also have $\text{wt}(x, 2) \text{ CO } r_1$ where $r_1 = \text{rd}(x)$ with $w_1 \text{ rf } r_1$ giving $w_2 \text{ CF } w_1$. Intuitively, we cannot find a total order amongst the writes to justify the reads of 1 and 2.

However, the program Fig.1(c) has a trace τ s.t. $\text{extend}_{\text{CCv}}(\tau)$ does not have **CCv** cycle. In the corresponding run, we first allow p_a to complete execution, followed by p_b .

Causal Memory CM. The **CM** model is stronger than **CC** and incomparable to **CCv**. Like **CC**, in **CM** also, a process can diverge from another one in its ordering of events which are not causally related. However, once a process chooses an ordering of such events, it cannot revise it; this makes it stronger than **CC** and incomparable to **CCv**.

A *happened before* relation per process fixes the per process ordering of events. For a read/write event e in a trace, the *Causal Past* of e , $\text{CausalPast}(e) = \{e' \mid e' \text{ CO } e\}$ is the set of events which are in the causal past of e . For an event e , the happened before relation HB_e [14] is the smallest relation on events which is transitive, and is such that for all events $e_1, e_2 \in \text{CausalPast}(e)$, $e_1 \text{ CO } e_2 \Rightarrow e_1 \text{ HB}_e e_2$. In other words, $\text{CO}|_{\text{CausalPast}(e)} \subseteq \text{HB}_e$: HB_e contains all pairs of events obtained by restricting **CO** to the events in the causal past of e . For any variable x , if we have writes w_1, w_2 on x and a read $r_2 = \text{rd}(x)$ such that

- (i) $r_2 = e$ or $r_2 \text{ po } e$, $w_2 \text{ rf } r_2$, and $w_1 \text{ HB}_e r_2$, then $w_1 \text{ HB}_e w_2$, and
- (ii) if $w_1 \text{ HB}_e w_2$ and $w_1 \text{ rf } r_2$, then $r \text{ HB}_e w_2$.

Let e_p be the *po*-last event of process p : that is, for all events e in process p , $e = e_p$ or $e \text{ po } e_p$. Since $\text{HB}_e \subseteq \text{HB}_{e_p}$ for all events e in process p , HB_{e_p} fixes the ordering among all causally unrelated events for process p . We write HB_p instead of HB_{e_p} .

We define a function $\text{extend}_{\text{CM}}$ which extends a trace $\tau = \langle E, \text{po}, \text{rf} \rangle$ by adding all possible **OW**, HB_p edges for all processes p . Traces violating **CM** exhibit a $\text{OW} \cup \text{HB}_p$ cycle, called a **CM** cycle in $\text{extend}_{\text{CM}}(\tau)$ for some process p . We say that $\tau \models \text{CM}$ iff $\text{extend}_{\text{CM}}(\tau)$ does not contain a **CM** cycle. See Figure 3 which motivates conditions (i), (ii) to add **HB** edges so that $\text{extend}_{\text{CM}}(\tau)$ does not contain **CM** cycle.

Examples. For the program Fig.1(c) and any trace τ , $\text{extend}_{\text{CM}}(\tau)$ contains **CM** cycle. Consider the read event $o_{p_b} = \text{rd}(x)$ with $\text{wt}(x, 2) \text{ rf } o_{p_b}$. Then $\text{wt}(x, 1) \text{ po } \text{wt}(y, 1) \text{ rf } \text{rd}(y) \text{ po } o_{p_b}$, that is, $\text{wt}(x, 1) \text{ CO } o_{p_b}$. This induces $\text{wt}(x, 1) \text{ HB}_{p_b} o_{p_b}$, and $\text{wt}(x, 1) \text{ HB}_{p_b} \text{wt}(x, 2)$. This results in $\text{wt}(z, 1) \text{ po } \text{wt}(x, 1) \text{ HB}_{p_b} \text{wt}(x, 2) \text{ po } r$ where $r = \text{rd}(z)$ with $\text{wt}(z, 0) \text{ rf } r$. This gives $\text{wt}(z, 1) \text{ HB}_{p_b} \text{wt}(z, 0)$ resulting in a cycle. However, program Fig.1(d) has a trace τ s.t. $\text{extend}_{\text{CM}}(\tau)$ does not contain **CM** cycle.

Fig. 3. Start with (a). In (b) we add the **HB** edge from $rd(z)$ to $wt(z, 2)$ following condition (ii). Then (c) is obtained on adding $rd(x), wt(x, 1)$ **rf** $rd(x)$. In contrast, (b)' does not follow condition (ii). Hence, when the $rd(x)$ is added in (c)', $wt(x, 2)$ is available to be read. Choosing $wt(x, 2)$ **rf** $rd(x)$ necessitates adding $wt(x, 1)$ **HB** $wt(x, 2)$ in (d)' by condition (i). This necessitates adding $wt(z, 2)$ **HB** $wt(z, 1)$ in (e)' creating **CM** cycle.

A run ρ satisfies a model $X \in \{\text{CC}, \text{CCv}, \text{CM}\}$ if there exists a trace τ such that $\rho \models \tau$ and $\tau \models X$. Define $\gamma_X := \{\tau_X \mid \exists \rho \in \text{Runs}(\gamma). \rho \models \tau_X \wedge \tau_X \models X\}$, the set of traces generated under X from a given configuration γ .

Note. Similar to our characterization of bad traces using cycles, [14] uses bad patterns in *differentiated histories* to capture violations of **CC**, **CCv**, **CM**. Differentiated histories are posets labeled with $wt(x, v)$ and $rd(x) \triangleright v$ such that no two events $wt(x, v_1)$ and $wt(x, v_2)$ have $v_1 = v_2$. Bad patterns are characterized in [14] using the **po** and reads from relations on differentiated histories. Since we work with traces having **po** and **rf**, we do not require differentiated writes.

4 Trace Semantics

To analyse a program \mathcal{P} under a model $X \in \{\text{CC}, \text{CCv}, \text{CM}\}$, all runs of \mathcal{P} must be explored. We do this by exploring the associated traces. In fact, two runs having the same associated traces are equivalent since the assertions to be checked at the end of a run depend only on **po**, **rf**. We begin with the empty trace, and continue exploration by adding enabled read/write events to the traces generated so far. While doing this, we must ensure that the generated traces τ are s.t. $\tau \models X$. We present two efficient operations to add a new read/write event to a trace τ obtaining a trace τ' so that $\text{extend}_X(\tau')$ does not contain a **X**cycle. We discuss two notions that are relevant while adding a new read event to a trace.

Readability and Visibility. For all 3 models, readability identifies the write events w from which a newly added read r can fetch its value. Visibility is used to add, in the case of **CCv**, new **CF** edges (and in the case of **CM**, new **HB** edges) that are implied by the fact that the new read event reads from w . Let $\tau = \langle \mathbf{E}, \text{po}, \text{rf} \rangle$ be a trace, and $\tau_X = \text{extend}_X(\tau)$. Let τ_X^r denote adding r to τ_X . We define the readable set $\text{readable}(\tau_X^r, r, x)$ for read event r from process p on variable x .

1. For $X = \text{CC}$, $\text{readable}(\tau_X^r, r, x)$ is defined as the set of all write events $w \in \mathbf{E}^{\text{wt}, x}$ s.t. there is no write $w' \in \mathbf{E}^{\text{wt}, x}$, s.t. $w \text{ CO } w' \text{ CO } r$ in τ_X^r .
2. For $X = \text{CCv}$, $\text{readable}(\tau_X^r, r, x)$ is defined as the set of all write events $w \in \mathbf{E}^{\text{wt}, x}$ s.t. there is no write $w' \in \mathbf{E}^{\text{wt}, x}$ s.t. $w \text{ (CO } \cup \text{ CF)}^+ w' \text{ CO } r$ in τ_X^r .
3. For $X = \text{CM}$, $\text{readable}(\tau_X^r, r, x)$ is defined as the set of all write events $w \in \mathbf{E}^{\text{wt}, x}$ s.t. there is no write $w' \in \mathbf{E}^{\text{wt}, x}$ s.t. $w \text{ HB}_p w' \text{ HB}_p r$ in τ_X^r .

Intuitively, $\text{readable}(\tau_X^r, r, x)$ contains all write events which are not hidden in τ_X^r by other writes on x . The newly added read event r can fetch its value from a write in $\text{readable}(\tau_X^r, r, x)$. The visible set $\text{visible}(\tau_X^r, r, x)$ is defined as the set of events in $\text{readable}(\tau_X^r, r, x)$ which can “reach” r in τ_X^r . Let τ^{rw} denote the trace obtained by adding r and w *rf* r to trace τ .

1. For $X = \text{CCv}$, $\text{visible}(\tau_X^r, r, x) = \{e \in \text{readable}(\tau_X^r, r, x) \mid e \text{ CO } r\}$. The point of $\text{visible}(\tau_X^r, r, x)$ is that when the new read r is added, which reads from a write w , $\text{extend}_X(\tau^{rw})$ will not contain $X\text{cycle}$ on adding from each $e \in \text{visible}(\tau_X^r, r, x)$ a **CF** edge to w . Then $\text{extend}_X(\tau^{rw})$ contains $\{(e, w) \mid e \in \text{visible}(\tau_X^r, r, x)\}$.
2. For $X = \text{CM}$, $\text{visible}(\tau_X^r, r, x) = \{e \in \text{readable}(\tau_X^r, r, x) \mid e \text{ HB}_p r\}$ where r is a read in process p . The point of $\text{visible}(\tau_X^r, r, x)$ is that when the new read r is added, which reads from a write w , $\text{extend}_X(\tau^{rw})$ will not contain $X\text{cycle}$ on adding from each $e \in \text{visible}(\tau_X^r, r, x)$ a **HB_p** edge to w . Then $\text{extend}_X(\tau^{rw})$ contains $\{(e, w) \mid e \in \text{visible}(\tau_X^r, r, x)\}$.

The *trace semantics* for a model $X \in \{\text{CC}, \text{CCv}, \text{CM}\}$ is given as the transition relation $\rightarrow_{X\text{-tr}}$, defined as $\tau_X \xrightarrow{\alpha}_{X\text{-tr}} \tau'_X$ where $\text{extend}_X(\tau) = \tau_X$, $\text{extend}_X(\tau') = \tau'_X$. The label α is one of (read, r, w) , (write, w) representing respectively, a read r reading from a write w , and a write event w . An important property of $\tau_X \xrightarrow{\alpha}_{X\text{-tr}} \tau'_X$ is that if τ_X does not have $X\text{cycle}$, then τ'_X also does not have $X\text{cycle}$; in other words, if $\tau \models X$, then $\tau' \models X$. We now describe the transitions $\tau_X \xrightarrow{\alpha}_{X\text{-tr}} \tau'_X$ where $\text{extend}_X(\tau) = \tau_X$, $\text{extend}_X(\tau') = \tau'_X$, $\tau = \langle \mathbf{E}, \text{po}, \text{rf} \rangle$, $\tau' = \langle \mathbf{E}', \text{po}', \text{rf}' \rangle$. We start from the empty trace τ_0 , $\text{extend}_X(\tau_0) = \tau_0$.

- From τ_X , assume that we observe a write w in process p . In this case, the label α is (write, w) , and we add w , and a **po** edge from the **po**-latest event of process p in τ_X to w obtaining τ'_X .
- From τ_X , assume we observe a read event r on variable x in process p . In this case, the label α is (read, r, w) , where w is the write from which r reads. Add the read r , a **po** edge from the **po**-latest event of process p in τ_X to r obtaining τ_X^r . Add *rf* from a $w \in \text{readable}(\tau_X^r, r, x)$ to r .
 - When $X = \text{CCv}$. Add new **CF** edges from all $w'' \in \text{visible}(\tau_X^r, r, x)$ to w to get τ'_X .
 - When $X = \text{CM}$. Add new **HB_p** edges from all $w'' \in \text{visible}(\tau_X^r, r, x)$ to w . Adding these **HB_p** edges can result in $w_1 \text{ HB}_p w_2$ for write events w_1, w_2 on a variable y . If we had $w_1 \text{ rf } r_1$, $r_1 \text{ po } r$, then add $r_1 \text{ HB}_p w_2$. When we are done adding all such **HB_p** edges, we obtain τ'_X . (Figure 4(iv)).

Lemma 1. *If $\tau_X = \text{extend}_X(\tau)$ with $\tau \models X$, and $\tau_X \xrightarrow{\alpha}_{X\text{-tr}} \tau'_X = \text{extend}_X(\tau')$, then $\tau' \models X$ for $X \in \{\text{CC}, \text{CCv}, \text{CM}\}$.*

Efficiency and Correctness. Each step of $\xrightarrow{\alpha}_{X\text{-tr}}$ is computable in polynomial time (see Appendix). This is based on the fact that readable and visible sets are computable in polynomial time. The correctness of the trace semantics for a

Fig. 4. w_1, w_6 are writes on y , r_1 is a read on y , w_2, w_3, w_4, w_5 are writes on x in τ_{CM} . Add read r on x to τ_{CM} . $w_2, w_3, w_5 \in \text{readable}(\tau_{\text{CM}}^r, r, x)$. Choose $w_5 \text{ rf } r$. Then we add $w_2 \text{ HB } w_5$ and $w_3 \text{ HB } w_5$. The addition of $w_2 \text{ HB } w_5$ results in $w_1 \text{ HB } w_6$. Since $w_1 \text{ rf } r_1$, add the HB edge from r_1 to w_6 to obtain τ'_{CM} .

Algorithm 1: EXPLORETRACES(X, τ_X, π)

Input: $X \in \{\text{CC}, \text{CCv}, \text{CM}\}$ is a consistency model, τ_X is an X -extension, π is an observation sequence.

- 1 **if** $\exists w \text{ s.t. } \tau_X \xrightarrow{\langle \text{write}, w \rangle} X\text{-tr}\tau'_X$ **then** // handle a write event
- 2 **let** $w = \text{wt}(x, v)$ and perform $\tau_X \xrightarrow{\langle \text{write}, w \rangle} X\text{-tr}\tau'_X$ // follow trace semantics write
- 3 EXPLORETRACES($X, \tau'_X, \pi \bullet w$)
- 4 CREATESCHEDULE($\tau'_X, \pi \bullet w$)
- 5 **else if** $\exists r \text{ s.t. } \tau_X \xrightarrow{\langle \text{read}, r, - \rangle} X\text{-tr}\tau'_X$ **then** // handle a read event
- 6 Schedules(r) $\leftarrow \emptyset$; Swappable(r) $\leftarrow \text{true}$
- 7 **for** $w, \tau'_X: \tau_X \xrightarrow{\langle \text{read}, r, w \rangle} X\text{-tr}\tau'_X$ **do** EXPLORETRACES($X, \tau'_X, \pi \bullet \langle r, w \rangle$) // follow trace semantics read
- 8 **for** $\beta \in \text{Schedules}(r)$ **do** RUNSCHEDULE(X, τ_X, π, β)

model X stems from the fact that it generates only those X -extensions which do not have cycles (Lemma 1). The design of the transitions ensures that the resultant extended trace does not have a cycle.

5 DPOR Algorithm for CC, CCv, CM

We present our DPOR algorithm, which systematically explores, for any terminating program under the consistency models $X \in \{\text{CC}, \text{CCv}, \text{CM}\}$, all traces τ_X wrt X which can be generated by the trace semantics. Enabled write events from any of the processes are added to the trace generated so far, and we proceed with the next event. For a read event r , we add r to the trace, and explore in separate branches, all possible write events w from which r can read from. Each such branch is a sequence of events also called a *schedule*. There may be writes w' which will be added to the trace later in the exploration, from

Algorithm 2: CREATESCHEDULE(X, τ_X, π)

Input: $X \in \{\text{CC}, \text{CCv}, \text{CM}\}$ is a consistency model, τ_X is an X -extension and π is an explored observation sequence.

```

1 let  $w$  be  $\text{last}(\pi)$  and  $x$  be  $\text{var}(w)$ 
2 for  $i \leftarrow |\pi| - 1$  to 1 do // look for reads  $r$  that have postponed  $w$ 
3   let  $r$  be the element at  $\pi[i]$ 
4   if  $r$  is a read on  $x \wedge \neg(r \text{ CO } w) \wedge \text{Swappable}(r)$  then
5      $\beta \leftarrow \epsilon$ ;  $\text{flag} = \text{true}$ ;
6     for  $j \leftarrow i + 1$  to  $|\pi| - 1$  do // get all events after  $r$  in  $\pi$  and
7       precedes  $w$  in CO
8       let  $ev$  be the element at  $\pi[j]$ 
9       if  $ev \text{ CO } w$  then
10        if  $r \text{ CO } ev$  then
11           $\text{flag} = \text{false}$ ; break;
12        else
13           $\beta \leftarrow \beta \bullet \pi[j]$ 
14    if  $\text{flag} \wedge \nexists \beta' \in \text{Schedules}(r). \beta' \approx \beta \bullet w \bullet \langle r, w \rangle$  then
15       $\text{Schedules}(r) \leftarrow \text{Schedules}(r) \cup \{\beta \bullet w \bullet \langle r, w \rangle\}$  //  $r$  can read
16      from  $w$ 

```

Algorithm 3: RUNSCHEDULE(X, τ_X, π, β)

Input: $X \in \{\text{CC}, \text{CCv}, \text{CM}\}$ is a consistency model, τ_X is a X -extension, π is an explored-observation sequence, and β is a schedule.

```

1 if  $\beta \neq \epsilon$  then // explore the sequence of observations one by one
2   let  $\beta$  be  $\alpha \bullet \beta'$  choose  $\tau'_X : \tau_X \xrightarrow{\alpha} X\text{-tr}\tau'_X$  // follow write and read
3   if  $\alpha = (\text{read}, r, w)$  then  $\text{Swappable}(r) \leftarrow \text{false}$ 
4   RUNSCHEDULE( $X, \tau'_X, \pi \bullet \alpha, \beta'$ )
5 else EXPLORETRACES( $X, \tau_X, \pi$ )

```

which r can also read. Such writes w' are called *postponed wrt r* ; when w' is added to the trace later, the algorithm will have a branch where r can read from w' . In that branch, the algorithm reorders events in the sequence s.t. w' and r exchange places, and all events which are needed for w' to occur are also placed before w' (CREATESCHEDULE). All generated schedules will be executed by RUNSCHEDULE. The algorithm is uniform across the models, with the main technical differences being taken care of by the respective trace semantics which guides the exploration of traces in each model.

The EXPLORETRACES Algorithm.

This algorithm takes as input, a consistency model $X \in \{\text{CC}, \text{CCv}, \text{CM}\}$, an X -extension τ_X and an *observation sequence* π . π is a sequence of events of the form (write, w) or (read, r, w) . The initial invocation is with the empty trace τ_0 and observation sequence $\pi = \epsilon$. The observation sequence is used to swap read operations with write operations that are *postponed wrt* them. From the initial τ_0 , we choose an operation from any of the processes.

If a write operation is enabled, one such is chosen non deterministically from any process, and is added to the trace according to the trace semantics, and also appended to the observation sequence, whereafter EXPLORETRACES is called recursively to continue the exploration (line 3). After the recursive calls have returned, the algorithm calls CREATESCHEDULE, which finds read operations r in the observation sequence which can read from write operations w if w was performed before r . For each such read r , CREATESCHEDULE creates a *schedule* for r , an observation sequence that can be explored from the point when r was performed, allowing w to occur before r so that r can read from w . When a read operation r is enabled, the set $\text{Schedules}(r)$ is initialized (line 6). This set is updated by CREATESCHEDULE when subsequent writes are explored. We also keep a Boolean flag $\text{Swappable}(r)$ for each read event r . This is initialized to true, indicating that r is swappable, that is, subsequent writes can be considered for r . This flag is set to false for read events appearing in a schedule so that they are not swapped, eliminating redundant explorations. For each generated write event w from which r can read, EXPLORETRACES is called recursively (line 7) to continue the exploration. Once these recursive calls have returned, the set of schedules collected in $\text{Schedules}(r)$ for the read r is considered. RUNSCHEDULE explores all schedules, where the read fetches its value from the respective write.

The CREATESCHEDULE algorithm. The input to this algorithm is a consistency model X , a trace τ_X wrt X , and an observation sequence π whose last element is a write. The algorithm looks for reads in π for which w is a postponed write. Indeed, this read r and w must be on the same variable, r must be swappable, and r must not precede w wrt CO (line 4). We begin with the closest (from the write w) such read r at position $\pi[j]$. After finding r , a schedule β is created. The schedule consists of all elements following r in π and preceding w wrt CO (line 12). It ends with $w \bullet (r, w)$, allowing r to read from w (line 13). This schedule is added to $\text{Schedules}(r)$ if it does not already contain a schedule β' which has the same set of observations : $\text{Schedules}(r)$ does not contain $\beta' \approx \beta$.

The RUNSCHEDULE Algorithm. The inputs are a consistency model X , a trace τ_X , an observation sequence π and a schedule β . The schedule of observations in β is explored one by one, by recursively calling itself, and updating the trace. The read events in the schedule are not swappable, preventing a redundant exploration for them (schedules where these are swapped with respective writes will be created by CREATESCHEDULE. Appendix A has an illustrative example.

Theorem 1. *Our DPOR algorithms are sound, complete and optimal.*

Soundness, Optimality and Completeness. The algorithm is sound in the sense that, if we initiate Algorithm 1 from (X, τ_0, ϵ) , then, all explored traces τ are s.t. $\tau \models X$. This follows from the fact that the exploration uses the $\rightarrow_{X\text{-tr}}$ relation. The algorithm is optimal in the sense that, for any two different recursive calls to Algorithm 1 with arguments (X, τ_X^1, π_1) and (X, τ_X^2, π_2) , if τ_X^1, τ_X^2 are extendible, then $\tau_X^1 \neq \tau_X^2$. This follows from (i) for a given read r , each iteration of the for loop in line 7 will correspond to a different write, (ii) in each schedule $\beta \in \text{Schedules}(e)$ in line 8 of Algorithm 1, the read event r reads

from a write w which is different from all writes it reads from in line 7 (iii) Any two schedules added to $\text{Schedules}(e)$ at line 14 of Algorithm 2 will be different. The algorithm is complete : all traces corresponding to terminating runs from the initial configuration are explored.

6 Experimental Evaluation

We describe the implementation of our optimal DPOR algorithm for the causal consistency models CC , CCv , CM as a tool **CONSCHECKER**, available at [45]. To the best of our knowledge, **CONSCHECKER** is the first stateless model checking tool for the causal consistency models CC , CCv , CM .

CONSCHECKER. **CONSCHECKER** extends **NIDHUGG** [2] and works at LLVM IR level accepting a C language program as input. At runtime, **CONSCHECKER** controls the exploration of the input program until it has explored all the traces using the DPOR algorithm. It can detect user-provided assertion violations by analyzing the generated traces. We conduct all experiments on a Ubuntu 22.04.1 LTS with Intel Core i7-1165G7 and 16 GB RAM. We evaluate **CONSCHECKER** on the following categories of benchmarks, as seen below.

Experimental Setup. We consider the following categories of benchmarks.

- A set of thousands of litmus tests (sec 6.1) generated from [7]. The main purpose of these experiments is to provide a sanity check of the correctness of **CONSCHECKER** on all three consistency models.
- A collection (sec 6.2) of concurrent benchmarks taken from the TACAS competition on software verification [44]. These are small programs with 50-100 lines of code used by many tools [3], [4].
- Five applications (sec 6.3) : Voter [19], Twitter clone [27], Fusion ticket [27], two versions of Auction [36], extracted from literature on databases, and verify against assertion violations wrt the three consistency models.
- Classical database benchmarks (sec 6.4) reported in recent papers on consistency models [12], [11] and [13]. We classify these benchmarks **SAFE** and **UNSAFE** on all three consistency models depending on whether they witness an assertion violation.
- Eight parameterized programs (sec 6.5) from [4] and [3] to study the scalability of **CONSCHECKER** when increasing the number of processes, as well as read and write instructions in programs.

6.1 Litmus Benchmarks

We apply **CONSCHECKER** on a set of 9815 litmus benchmarks generated from [7]. Litmus tests are standard benchmark programs used by many tools running on weak memories. In these litmus tests, the processes execute concurrently, and we validate assertions on the underlying memory model, doing a sanity check for the correctness of **CONSCHECKER**. We compared the observed outcomes of **CONSCHECKER** on the litmus tests with expected outcomes generated from [7]. We generated the expected outcomes by simulating the CCv , and CC and CM

Table 1. Classical benchmarks

Program	CCv	CC	CM
Causality Violation [12]	UNSAFE	UNSAFE	UNSAFE
Causal Violation [13]	SAFE	SAFE	SAFE
Delivery Order [11]	UNSAFE	UNSAFE	SAFE
Long Fork [12]	UNSAFE	UNSAFE	UNSAFE
Lost Update [12]	UNSAFE	UNSAFE	UNSAFE
Message Passing [10]	SAFE	SAFE	SAFE
Conflict violation [13]	UNSAFE	UNSAFE	UNSAFE
Read Atomicity [13]	UNSAFE	UNSAFE	UNSAFE
Repeated Read [13]	UNSAFE	UNSAFE	UNSAFE
Load Buffer	SAFE	SAFE	SAFE
Store Buffer [10]	UNSAFE	UNSAFE	UNSAFE
Write Skew [12]	UNSAFE	UNSAFE	UNSAFE

Table 2. Applications.

App	Time
Vote [19]	1s
Twitter clone [27]	0.09s
FusionTicket [27]	0.75s
Auction [36]	0.11s
Auction-2 [36]	1.17s
Group	0.10s

Table 3. SV-Comp Benchmarks

Program	CCv		CC		CM	
	Traces	Time	Traces	Time	Traces	Time
Lamport	15669	3s	2904225	490s	299028	110s
Szymanski	1023397	131s	1023397	115s	1023397	190s
Peterson	5371	1s	13483	1s	12316	1.5s
Fibonacci	6224342	769s	6224342	695s	6224342	1796s
Dekker	86267	7s	1549862	155s	107698	18s

semantics on [7] for these litmus tests. Out of the 9815 litmus tests, we found no assertion violations in 3810 under CC, CM and 3811 under CCv. Results obtained from CONSCHECKER matched with the expected outcomes. CONSCHECKER took <3 mins to execute on all litmus tests across models.

6.2 SV-COMP Benchmarks

These benchmarks [44] consist of five programs written in C/C++ having 2 processes each, with 50-100 lines of code per process (Table 3). The main challenge in these benchmarks is the large number of traces to be explored. These benchmarks have assertion checks, and under CCv, CM, and CC all these assertions are violated. CONSCHECKER stops exploration as soon as it detects the first assertion violation. To check the efficiency of CONSCHECKER, we removed all assertions and let CONSCHECKER exhaustively explore all possible traces following *po* and *rf* relations. Since these benchmarks have large number of traces, they serve as a stress test for CONSCHECKER.

6.3 Database Applications

Table 2 reports the performance of CONSCHECKER on a set of programs inspired from five applications extracted from the literature on distributed systems [19], [27], [11], [36]. The applications we considered are

Table 4. Parameterized Benchmarks from [4] and [3]

Program	CC		CCv		CM	
	Traces	Time	Traces	Time	Traces	Time
control-flow(6)	77	0.05s	77	0.05s	77	0.05s
control-flow(8)	273	0.07s	273	0.06s	273	0.10s
control-flow(10)	1045	0.16s	1045	0.12s	1045	0.33s
control-flow(12)	4121	0.60s	4121	0.45s	4121	1.80s
n-writers-a-read(5)	6	0.05s	6	0.05s	6	0.05s
n-writers-a-read(10)	11	0.05s	11	0.05s	11	0.05s
n-writers-a-read(15)	16	0.05s	16	0.05	16	0.05s
n-writers-a-read(20)	21	0.05s	21	0.05	21	0.05s
redundant-co(5)	91	0.07s	91	0.05s	91	0.05s
redundant-co(10)	331	0.09s	331	0.05s	331	0.08s
redundant-co(15)	721	0.11s	721	0.08s	721	0.12a
redundant-co(20)	1261	0.18	1261	0.13s	1261	0.20s
casrot(9)	8579	0.55s	8597	0.77s	8597	2s
casrot(10)	38486	2.50s	38486	3.16s	38486	9s
casrot(11)	182905	14s	182905	16s	182905	49s
floating-read(9)	10	0.05s	10	0.05s	10	0.05s
floating-read(11)	12	0.05s	12	0.05s	12	0.05s
floating-read(13)	14	0.05s	14	0.05s	14	0.05s
lastwrite(9)	9	0.04s	9	0.04s	9	0.04s
lastwrite(11)	11	0.04s	11	0.04	11	0.04s
lastwrite(13)	13	0.04	13	0.04	13	0.04s
lastzero(9)	1536	0.18s	1536	0.20s	1536	0.33s
lastzero(11)	7168	1s	7168	1s	7168	2s
lastzero(13)	32768	5s	32768	5s	32768	12s
readers(9)	512	0.10s	512	0.10s	512	0.18s
readers(11)	2048	0.40s	2048	0.35s	2048	1s
readers(13)	8192	1.5s	8192	1.5s	8192	6s

- Voter [19] : This application is derived from a software system used to record votes from a talent show. Users can vote for any of the n contestants from any one of the m sites (processes). The application asserts that users cannot vote from multiple sites and cannot vote for multiple contestants and checks for violations of this. [19] considers 3 sites and 3 users, and we follow suit.
- Twitter clone [27] : This is based on a twitter like service where each user has some followers. The following assertion is checked : when the user tweets, the tweet ID must be added to the follower’s time line exactly once if the user did not remove his tweet. We considered 3 users using 3 processes, each process has 10 tweet IDs and 6 followers.
- Fusion ticket [27] : There is a building having multiple concert rooms (venues). Tickets for venue i are sold by salesperson i who updates in the backend database, the sales for the day. The per venue ticket sale must be updated correctly in the database, so that the concert manager sees the correct total number of tickets sold. A discrepancy in this number is a violation. Each venue is represented

by a process, and the communication across processes ensures the total sum is correct. We considered 4 venues and each venue had 10 tickets.

- Auction [36] and Auction-2 [36]: There are n bidders and an auctioneer participating in an auction, modeled using $n + 1$ processes. The assertion to be checked is that the highest bidder must be declared winner. Auction is the buggy version for this application, while Auction-2 is the correct one.
- Group is a synthetic application created by us inspired from whatsapp groups. There is a group with n members, and a new person wants to be added to the group. This person must be added to the group only by one of the existing members. That is, a violation constitutes to adding a person more than once (by one or more members). We check with 6 processes(members).

6.4 Classical Benchmarks

Table 1 consists of classical benchmarks [12], [13], [11] and [10] which test for some assertion violations under the three models. Since the traces generated differ for each model $X \in \{\text{CC}, \text{CCv}, \text{CM}\}$, the violations also differ. For the ones marked SAFE under model $X \in \{\text{CC}, \text{CCv}, \text{CM}\}$, the assertion violation did not occur under any execution, while the unsafe ones reported the violation. We consider twenty such examples. The appendix has some variants obtained by considering three different versions of each example, varying the number of processes and variables.

In the appendix, for each example, we have three versions by parameterizing the number of processes and instructions. In version 1, we have four processes per program and three to five instructions per process. Version 2 is obtained allowing each process to have seven-ten instructions. Version 3 expands version 2 by allowing each program to have up to five-six processes and up to 15-20 instructions. The number of instructions is increased by introducing fresh variables and having reads/writes on them. Versions 2,3 serve as a stress test for CONSCHECKER as increasing the number of instructions and processes increases the number of of consistent traces. CONSCHECKER took less than 3s to finish running all version 1 programs, about 30s to finish running all version 2 programs and about 200s to finish running all version 3 programs.

6.5 Parameterized Benchmarks

Table 4 reports experimental results of CONSCHECKER on 8 parameterized benchmarks. Out of these, in redundant-co(N) (taken from [4]), N is the number of loop iterations per process in a program with 3 processes. In all others, the parameterization is on the number of processes. This set of benchmarks serves to check the scalability of CONSCHECKER. As seen in Table 4, CONSCHECKER scales up to 20 processes (n-writers-a-read) and 13 variables (lastzero).

7 Conclusion

In this paper, we have provided a DPOR algorithm using the *po-rf* equivalence for three prominent causal consistency models, and also implemented the same

in a tool CONSCHECKER. This is the first tool for stateless model checking of causal consistency models. We plan to extend our work by developing a DPOR algorithm for transactional programs under CC , CCv , CM [11]. For these, the extra complication is the presence of transactions which must be executed atomically without interference in each process. The final notch is to handle snapshot isolation, the strongest among transactional consistency models.

8 Data-Availability Statement

The tool and experimental data for the study are available at the Zenodo repository: [45].

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Appendix

A Illustrating Example for DPOR

Fig. 5. Program

We illustrate the DPOR algorithm on Figure 5. We have presented the recursion tree in Figure 6 for execution under CM semantics. Figure 7 gives the traces τ_2 and τ_3 generated during the algorithm execution. Node n_0 is the initial call to EXPLORETRACES with an empty trace and observation sequence. Then the algorithm visits the write events from the till node n_3 . At this point the algorithm visits $d = z$. Since there are two writes on z and both are readable, the algorithm creates two paths (line 7 of Algorithm 1). Assume the read is $d = z \triangleright 1$ (node n_4). Next, the algorithm visits the read events $a = y \triangleright 0$, $b = x \triangleright 2$ and $c = z \triangleright 2$. Next it visits the write event $x = 1$ and then $y = 1$. This completes the trace τ_1 . Since there are no more events to execute, the recursive call from node n_9 returns. Since $y = 1$ is a read event, CREATESCHEDULE function is invoked. This call to CREATESCHEDULE for $y = 1$ finds the read candidate $a = y$ and creates schedule $\beta_1 = \{c = z; x = 1; y = 1; a = y\}$ and adds it to the Schedule($a = y$). The recursive call returns to node n_6 . Then again CREATESCHEDULE is invoked. The call CREATESCHEDULE will create the schedule $\beta_2 = \{c = z; x = 1; b = x\}$ and adds β_2 to Schedule($b = x$) and returns to the node n_5 . Since there are no other readable writes for $b = x$, the algorithm will look for the schedules in Schedule($b = x$) (line 8 of Algorithm 1). Schedule($b = x$) contains the schedule $\beta_2 = \{c = z; x = 1; b = x\}$. Hence, the function RUNSCHEDULE is invoked for β_2 . RUNSCHEDULE will run schedule β_2 represented by violet edges in 6 from n_5 . After running β_2 , RUNSCHEDULE invokes EXPLORETRACES. Then $y = 1$ is visited. This completes trace τ_2 . At

Fig. 6. Recursive exploration of the program 5 under CM semantics. Black edges and corresponding nodes represent the recursive calls of EXPLORETRACES. Orange edges represent the schedules created during CREATESCHEDULE and violet edges represent running these created schedules.

n_{12} , CREATESCHEDULE is invoked for $y = 1$. This call to CREATESCHEDULE will create schedule $\beta_3 = \{c = z; x = 1; y = 1; a = y\}$ for $a = y$. But $\text{Schedule}(a = y)$ contains schedule β_2 equivalent to β_3 . Hence β_3 will not be added to $\text{Schedule}(a = y)$ (line 13, Algorithm 2). Then the call returns to n_4 . For $a = y$, $\text{Schedule}(a = y)$ has schedule $\beta_1 = \{c = z; x = 1; y = 1; a = y\}$. Hence, RUNSCHEDULE is invoked for β_1 and we get nodes n_{13} to n_{16} represented in violet edges. We complete trace τ_3 by executing $b = x$ (node n_{17}). The recursive call returns to n_3 , and node n_{18} is created for the read $d = z \triangleright 2$ (line 7, Algorithm 1). From this node, the algorithm keeps exploring the traces and generates a total of four traces for τ_4, τ_5, τ_6 , and τ_7 . Then the algorithm terminates. Therefore, under CM semantics the DPOR algorithm will generate seven traces for 5.

Running the DPOR algorithm under CM and CCv for 5 will generate eight traces, as shown in Figure 8. This eighth trace τ_8 (completed at node n') is not CM consistent.

Fig. 7. τ_2 and τ_3 traces generated for the program (Figure 5) in Figure 6

B Efficiency of Computing Readable and Visible Sets

B.1 We can compute readable and visible sets in polynomial time

Proof. Let $\mathcal{T} = E$. We prove that set $\text{readable}(X, \tau, r, x)$ can be computed in polynomial time by designing an algorithm to generate set $\text{readable}(X, \tau, r, x)$. The algorithm consists of the following steps:

- (i) First we compute the transitive closure of the relations $[po \cup rf]$ and $[po \cup rf \cup CF]$, i.e, we compute $[po \cup rf \cup CF]^+$ and $[po \cup rf]^+$. We can use the Floyd-Warshall algorithm [18] to compute the transitive closure. This will take $O(|\mathcal{T}|^3)$ time.
- (ii) We compute the set $\mathcal{T}' = \{e \mid e[po \cup rf]^+ r\}$. This takes $O(|\mathcal{T}|^2)$ time.
- (iii) For each write event $e \in E^{w,x}$, we perform following check:
 - Check **cond** : Check whether there exists a write event $e' \in \mathcal{T}'$, $e \neq e'$ such that $e [po \cup rf \cup CF]^+ e'$.
If we find such e' , then $e \notin \text{readable}(X, \tau, t, x)$.
Else add e the readable set $\text{readable}(X, \tau, r, x)$.
This step will take $O(|\mathcal{T}|^2)$ time.

Similarly, we can compute $\text{visible}(\tau, t, x)$ in polynomial time. This completes the proof.

Fig. 8. Traces generated by CC and CCv DPOR for program given in Figure 5

C Details for CCv

C.1 Properties of trace semantics for CCv

Lemma 2. *For extended traces $\tau_{\text{CCv}}^1 = \text{extend}_{\text{CCv}}(\tau^1)$ and $\tau_{\text{CCv}}^2 = \text{extend}_{\text{CCv}}(\tau^2)$ if $\tau_{\text{CCv}}^1 \xrightarrow{\text{read}(r,w)}_{\text{tr}} \tau_{\text{CCv}}^2$ and $\tau^1 \models \text{CCv}$, then $\tau^2 \models \text{CCv}$.*

Proof. Let $\tau_{\text{CCv}}^1 = \text{extend}_{\text{CCv}}(\tau^1)$ and $\tau_{\text{CCv}}^2 = \text{extend}_{\text{CCv}}(\tau^2)$. Let r be the read event and let $w \in \text{readable}(\tau_{\text{CCv}}^1, r, x)$ be the chosen write event that e reads from, while $\tau_{\text{CCv}}^1 \xrightarrow{\text{read}(r,w)}_{\text{tr}} \tau_{\text{CCv}}^2$. Then, $\mathbf{E}_2 = \mathbf{E}_1 \cup r$, $\mathbf{rf}_2 = \mathbf{rf}_1 \cup (w, r)$ and $\mathbf{CF}_2 = \mathbf{CF}_1 \cup \{(w', w) \mid w' \in \text{visible}(\tau, r, x)\}$.

First we show that, if there are events e_1, e_2 and e_3 such that $e_1 \mathbf{CF}_2 e_3$ and $e_2 \mathbf{rf}_2 e_3$. then $e_1 \mathbf{CF}_2 e_2$. Since e has no successor in $[\mathbf{po} \cup \mathbf{rf} \cup \mathbf{CF}]^+$, we need to consider following scenarios.

- ★ $y = x, e_3 = r, e_2 = w$ and there is a event $e_4 \in \text{visible}(\tau_{\text{CCv}}^1, r, x)$ such that $e_1 \mathbf{CF}_1 e_4$. By definition of $\tau_{\text{CCv}}^1 \xrightarrow{\text{read}(r,w)}_{\text{tr}} \tau_{\text{CCv}}^2$, we have $e_4 \mathbf{CF}_2 e'$. Hence, it follows that $e_1 \mathbf{CF}_2 e_2$.
- ★ $y = x$ and there is an event $e_4 \in \text{visible}(\tau_{\text{CCv}}^1, r, x)$. $e_1 \mathbf{CF}_2 e_3$ is obtained because of $e_4 \mathbf{CF}_2 e'$. That is, $e_1 \mathbf{CF}_1 e_4 \mathbf{CF}_2 e' \mathbf{CF}_1 e_3$. Since, $e' \mathbf{CF}_1 e_3$ and $e_2 \mathbf{rf}_1^x e_3$, we have $e' \mathbf{CF}_1 e_2$. Since $\tau_2 \sqsubseteq \tau_1$, it follows that $e' \mathbf{CF}_2 e_2$ and $e_1 \mathbf{CF}_2 e_4$ Hence, we have $e_1 \mathbf{CF}_2 e_4 \mathbf{CF}_2 e_2$.

Suppose that $\tau^2 \not\models \text{CCv}$. That means there is a cycle $w [\mathbf{po}_2 \cup \mathbf{rf}_2 \cup \mathbf{CF}_2]^+ w'$ in τ_{CCv}^2 . Since $\tau^1 \models \text{CCv}$ we have $w [\mathbf{po}_1 \cup \mathbf{rf}_1 \cup \mathbf{CF}_1]^+ w'$ for some $w' \in \text{visible}(\tau_{\text{CCv}}^1, r, x)$. This contradicts the fact that $w \in \text{readable}(\tau_{\text{CCv}}^1, r, x)$.

Hence $\tau_2 \models \text{CCv}$.

Lemma 3. *For extended traces $\tau_{\text{CCv}}^1 = \text{extend}_{\text{CCv}}(\tau^1)$ and $\tau_{\text{CCv}}^2 = \text{extend}_{\text{CCv}}(\tau^2)$ if $\tau_{\text{CCv}}^1 \xrightarrow{\text{write}(w)}_{\text{tr}} \tau_{\text{CCv}}^2$ and $\tau^1 \models \text{CCv}$, then $\tau^2 \models \text{CCv}$.*

Proof. The proof follows from the definition of $\xrightarrow{\text{write}(w)}_{\text{tr}}$.

Notation Alert: In the following and beyond, we use the notation $(\langle \mathbf{E}, \mathbf{po}, \mathbf{rf} \rangle, \mathbf{CF})$ to denote an extended trace $\text{extend}_{\text{CCv}}(\tau)$ where $\tau = \langle \mathbf{E}, \mathbf{po}, \mathbf{rf} \rangle$. We also extend the notation $\tau \models \text{CCv}$ to $\text{extend}_{\text{CCv}}(\tau) \models \text{CCv}$ whenever $\text{extend}_{\text{CCv}}(\tau)$ does not contain CCv cycle.

C.2 CCv DPOR Soundness Proof

To prove soundness, we first define a new semantics called *incremental semantics*.

CCv incremental semantics We define a new *incremental semantics* for CCv. In *incremental semantics* each trace gives the total order of the write events per variable for each process. To define the semantics we introduce notation $\xrightarrow{\alpha}_{\text{Inc}}$ on extended traces.

- Transition $\tau_1 \xrightarrow{\text{write}(w)}_{\text{Inc}} \tau_2$ where w is a write event in p , $\tau_1 = ((E_1, \text{po}_1, \text{rf}_1), \text{CF}_1)$, $\tau_2 = ((E_2, \text{po}_2, \text{rf}_2), \text{CF}_2)$, $E_2 = E_1 \cup w$, $\text{po}_2 = \text{po}_1 \cup (epow)$, $\text{rf}_2 = \text{rf}_1$, $\text{CF}_1 \subseteq \text{CF}_2$ and CF_2 gives total order over all write events per variable.
- Transition $\tau_1 \xrightarrow{\text{read}(r,w)}_{\text{Inc}} \tau_2$ where $r \in p$ is event reading from w , $\tau_1 = ((E_1, \text{po}_1, \text{rf}_1), \text{CF}_1)$, $\tau_2 = ((E_2, \text{po}_2, \text{rf}_2), \text{CF}_2)$, $E_2 = E_1 \cup r$, $\text{po}_2 = \text{po}_1 \cup (e\text{po}r)$, $\text{rf}_2 = \text{rf}_1 \cup (w, r)$, $\text{CF}_2 = \text{CF}_1$.
In this transition, $r = \text{rd}(x) \in p$ reads from the last write w in the total order CF for x .

We define $\gamma^{\text{Inc}} = \{\tau \mid \tau_\emptyset \rightarrow_{\text{Inc}} \tau\}$ as the set of extended traces $\tau = ((E, \text{po}, \text{rf}), \text{CF})$ for the given program obtained by starting from the configurations γ and empty trace τ_\emptyset . We define $\gamma_{\text{CCv}}^{\text{Inc}} := \{\tau \in \gamma^{\text{Inc}} \mid \tau \models \text{CCv}\}$, i.e. $\gamma_{\text{CCv}}^{\text{Inc}}$ is set of CCv consistent trace extensions generated using *incremental semantics*.

We define $\gamma^{\text{tr}} = \{\tau \mid \tau_\emptyset \rightarrow_{\text{tr}} \tau\}$ as the set of trace extensions $\tau = ((E, \text{po}, \text{rf}), \text{CF})$ for the given program obtained by starting from the empty trace τ_\emptyset and configuration γ . We define $\gamma_{\text{CCv}}^{\text{tr}} := \{\tau \in \gamma^{\text{tr}} \mid \tau \models \text{CCv}\}$, i.e. $\gamma_{\text{CCv}}^{\text{tr}}$ is set of CCv consistent traces generated using *trace semantics*.

Recall that $\gamma_{\text{CCv}} := \{\tau_{\text{CCv}} \mid \exists \rho \text{Runs}(\gamma). \rho \models \tau_{\text{CCv}} \wedge \tau_{\text{CCv}} \models \text{CCv}\}$ is set of traces generated under CCv from a given configuration γ .

Lemma 4. $\gamma_{\text{CCv}}^{\text{Inc}} = \gamma_{\text{CCv}}$.

We prove the soundness of CCv DPOR in two parts: (I) $\{\tau \mid (\tau, \text{CF}) \in \gamma_{\text{CCv}}^{\text{tr}}\} \subseteq \{\tau \mid (\tau, \text{CF}) \in \gamma_{\text{CCv}}^{\text{Inc}}\}$ and (II) $\{\tau \mid (\tau, \text{CF}) \in \gamma_{\text{CCv}}^{\text{Inc}}\} \subseteq \{\tau = \mid (\tau, \text{CF}) \in \gamma_{\text{CCv}}^{\text{tr}}\}$.

C.3 $\{\tau \mid (\tau, \text{CF}) \in \gamma_{\text{CCv}}^{\text{tr}}\} \subseteq \{\tau \mid (\tau, \text{CF}) \in \gamma_{\text{CCv}}^{\text{Inc}}\}$

Lemma 5. If $\tau_1 \xrightarrow{\text{write}(w)}_{\text{tr}} \tau_2$, $\tau_2 \sqsubseteq \tau_4$, and τ_4 gives total order of write events per variable then there exists a τ_3 such that $\tau_3 \xrightarrow{\text{write}(w)}_{\text{Inc}} \tau_4$ and $\tau_1 \sqsubseteq \tau_3$.

Proof. Let $\tau_1 = ((E_1, \text{po}_1, \text{rf}_1), \text{CF}_1)$, $\tau_2 = ((E_2, \text{po}_2, \text{rf}_2), \text{CF}_2)$ and $\tau_4 = ((E_4, \text{po}_4, \text{rf}_4), \text{CF}_4)$. Since $\tau_2 \sqsubseteq \tau_4$, we have $\text{po}_2 = \text{po}_4$, $\text{rf}_4 = \text{rf}_2$ and $\text{CF}_2 \sqsubseteq \text{CF}_4$. We have $E_2^w = E_1^w \cup w$, $\text{po}_2 = \text{po}_1 \cup \{e\text{po}w\}$, $\text{rf}_2 = \text{rf}_1$ and $\text{CF}_1 = \text{CF}_2$.

Define $\tau_3 = ((E_3, \text{po}_3, \text{rf}_3), \text{CF}_3)$ where $E_3 = E_1$, $\text{rf}_3 = \text{rf}_1 = \text{rf}_4|_{E_3}$ and $\text{CF}_3 = \text{CF}_4|_{E_3}$. It follows that $\tau_3 \xrightarrow{\text{write}(w)}_{\text{Inc}} \tau_4$. We need to show that $\text{CF}_1 \subseteq \text{CF}_3$. Consider $e \in \text{CF}_1$. Since $\text{CF}_1 \subseteq \text{CF}_2$ and $\text{CF}_2 \subseteq \text{CF}_4$. Since $e, e' \in E_1 = E_3$ and $\text{CF}_3 = \text{CF}_4|_{E_3}$, we have $e \in \text{CF}_3$.

Lemma 6. If $\tau_1 \xrightarrow{\text{read}(r,w)}_{\text{tr}} \tau_2$, $\tau_2 \sqsubseteq \tau_4$, and τ_4 gives total order of write events per variable then there exists a τ_3 such that $\tau_3 \xrightarrow{\text{read}(r,w)}_{\text{Inc}} \tau_4$ and $\tau_1 \sqsubseteq \tau_3$.

Proof. Let $\tau_1 = ((E_1, po_1, rf_1), CF_1)$, $\tau_2 = ((E_2, po_2, rf_2), CF_2)$ and $\tau_4 = ((E_4, po_4, rf_4), CF_4)$. Since $\tau_1 \sqsubseteq \tau_2$, we have $po_2 = po_1$, $rf_2 = rf_1$ and $CF_2 \sqsubseteq CF_1$. We have $E_2 = E_1 \cup r$, $po_2 = po_1 \cup \{e \text{ po } r\}$, $rf_2 = rf_1 \cup (w, r)$ and $CF_2 = \{(w', w) \mid w' \in \text{visible}(\tau_1, r, x)\}$.

Define $\tau_3 = ((E_3, po_3, rf_3), CF_3)$ where $E_3 = E_1$, $rf_3 = rf_1$ and $CF_3 = CF_1|_{E_3}$. It follows that $\tau_3 \xrightarrow{\text{read}(r,w)}_{\text{Inc}} \tau_4$. We need to show that $CF_1 \sqsubseteq CF_3$. Consider $e \in CF_1$. Since $CF_1 \sqsubseteq CF_2$ and $CF_2 \sqsubseteq CF_4$. Since $e \in E_1 = E_3$ and $CF_3 = CF_1|_{E_3}$, we have $e \in CF_3$.

Lemma 7. *If $\tau_1 \xrightarrow{*}_{\text{tr}} \tau_2$, $\tau_2 \sqsubseteq \tau_4$ and τ_4 gives total order of write events for each process then there exists a τ_3 such that $\tau_3 \xrightarrow{*}_{\text{Inc}} \tau_4$ and $\tau_1 \sqsubseteq \tau_3$.*

Proof. Follows from Lemmas 5 and 6.

Lemma 8. $\{\tau \mid (\tau, CF) \in \gamma_{\text{CCv}}^{\text{tr}}\} \subseteq \{\tau \mid (\tau, CF) \in \gamma_{\text{CCv}}^{\text{Inc}}\}$

Proof. Assume $\tau \in \gamma_{\text{CCv}}^{\text{tr}}$. We show that there is trace $\tau' \in \gamma_{\text{CCv}}^{\text{Inc}}$, such that $\tau \sqsubseteq \tau'$.

Since $\tau \in \gamma_{\text{CCv}}^{\text{tr}}$, we know that $\tau_0 \xrightarrow{*}_{\text{tr}} \tau$. That is, there is a sequence $\tau_0 \xrightarrow{\alpha}_{\text{tr}} \tau_1 \xrightarrow{\alpha}_{\text{tr}} \tau_2 \cdots \xrightarrow{\alpha}_{\text{tr}} \tau_n$, where $\tau_0 = \tau_0$ and $\tau_n = \tau$. Since τ_0 is empty relation, hence $\tau_0 \models \text{CCv}$. Since we generated traces $\tau_1, \tau_2 \cdots \tau_n$ by following *trace semantics* transitions from τ_0 , $\tau_1, \tau_2 \cdots \tau_n$ are CCv consistent. From Lemma 7 there is a sequence $\tau'_0 \xrightarrow{\alpha}_{\text{Inc}} \tau'_1 \xrightarrow{\alpha}_{\text{Inc}} \tau'_2 \cdots \xrightarrow{\alpha}_{\text{Inc}} \tau'_n$, where $\tau'_0 = \tau_0$ and $\tau'_n = \tau$ such that $\tau_i \sqsubseteq \tau'_i$, $i : 1$ to n . Thus we have $\tau'_0 \xrightarrow{*}_{\text{Inc}} \tau'$ and $\tau \sqsubseteq \tau'$. Hence, $\tau \in \gamma_{\text{CCv}}^{\text{Inc}}$.

C.4 $\{\tau \mid (\tau, CF) \in \gamma_{\text{CCv}}^{\text{Inc}}\} \subseteq \{\tau \mid (\tau, CF) \in \gamma_{\text{CCv}}^{\text{tr}}\}$

Lemma 9. $\tau_1 \xrightarrow{\text{read}(r,w)}_{\text{Inc}} \tau_2$ and $\tau_2 \models \text{CCv}$, then $w \in \text{readable}(\tau_1, r, x)$.

Proof. Let $\tau_1 = ((E_1, po_1, rf_1), CF_1)$, $\tau_2 = ((E_2, po_2, rf_2), CF_2)$ and let $r \in p$. Assume $w \notin \text{readable}(\tau_1, r, x)$. That means, there a event $e \in E^{w,x}$ such that $w [po_1 \cup rf_1 \cup CF_1]^+ e$ and $e [po_2 \cup rf_2]^+ r$. Since CF gives the total order for write events on the same variable, if $e \in CF_1$ w , then we get $e \in CF_2$ $w [po_1 \cup rf_1 \cup CF_1]^+ e$. This means that $\tau_1 \not\models \text{CCv}$, i.e $\tau_2 \not\models \text{CCv}$. This is a contradiction to the fact that $\tau_2 \models \text{CCv}$. If $w \notin CF_1$ e , since $w \in rf_2$ r and $e [po_1 \cup rf_1]^+ r$ we add CF edge from e to w (by definition of extensions). This will create a cycle. This is a contradiction to the fact that $\tau_2 \models \text{CCv}$.

Lemma 10. *If $\tau_1 \sqsubseteq \tau_2$ and $w \in \text{readable}(\tau_2, r, x)$ then $w \in \text{readable}(\tau_1, r, x)$.*

Proof. Since $w \in \text{readable}(\tau_2, r, x)$, there is no write event such that $w [po_2 \cup rf_2 \cup CF_2]^+ e [po_2 \cup rf_2]^+ r$. Since $\tau_1 \sqsubseteq \tau_2$, we have $[po_1 \cup rf_1 \cup CF_1]^+ \subseteq [po_2 \cup rf_2 \cup CF_2]^+$. Hence, there is no write event e such that $w [po_1 \cup rf_1 \cup CF_1]^+ e [po_1 \cup rf_1]^+ r$. Therefore, $w \in \text{readable}(\tau_1, r, x)$.

Lemma 11. *If $\tau_1 \xrightarrow{\text{write}(w)}_{\text{Inc}} \tau_2$, and $\tau_3 \sqsubseteq \tau_1$, then there exists $\tau_3 \xrightarrow{\text{write}(w)}_{\text{tr}} \tau_4$ and $\tau_4 \sqsubseteq \tau_2$.*

Proof. Let $\tau_1 = (E_1, po_1, rf_1, CF_1)$, $\tau_2 = (E_2, po_2, rf_2, CF_2)$ and $\tau_3 = (E_3, po_3, rf_3, CF_3)$. Since $\tau_3 \sqsubseteq \tau_1$, we have $po_3 = po_1$, $rf_3 = rf_1$ and $CF_3 \subseteq CF_1$. We have $E_2 = E_1 \cup \{w\}$, $po_2 = po_1 \cup \{(e, w) \mid (e \text{ po } w)\}$, $rf_2 = rf_1$ and $CF_1 \subseteq CF_2$ and CF_2 gives total order on write events.

Define $\tau_4 = (E_4, po_4, rf_4, CF_4)$ where $E_4 = E_3 \cup \{(e, w) \mid (e \text{ po } w)\}$, $rf_4 = rf_3 \cup (w, r)$ and $CF_4 = CF_3$. It follows that $\tau_3 \xrightarrow{\text{write}(w)}_{\text{tr}} \tau_4$. Since $CF_3 \subseteq CF_1 \subseteq CF_2$, we have $CF_4 \subseteq CF_2$. Hence, $\tau_4 \sqsubseteq \tau_2$.

Lemma 12. *If $\tau_1 \xrightarrow{\text{read}(r,w)}_{\text{Inc}} \tau_2$, and $\tau_3 \sqsubseteq \tau_1$, then there exists $\tau_3 \xrightarrow{\text{read}(r,w)}_{\text{tr}} \tau_4$ and $\tau_4 \sqsubseteq \tau_2$.*

Proof. Let $\tau_1 = (E_1, po_1, rf_1, CF_1)$, $\tau_2 = (E_2, po_2, rf_2, CF_2)$ and $\tau_3 = (E_3, po_3, rf_3, CF_3)$. Since $\tau_3 \sqsubseteq \tau_1$, we have $po_3 = po_1$, $rf_3 = rf_1$ and $CF_3 \subseteq CF_1$. We have $E_2 = E_1 \cup r$, $po_2 = po_1 \cup \{(e, r) \mid (e \text{ por})\}$, $rf_2 = rf_1 \cup (w, r)$ and $CF_1 \subseteq CF_2$ and CF_2 gives total order on write events.

Define $\tau_4 = (E_4, po_4, rf_4, CF_4)$ where $E_4 = E_3 \cup \{(e, r) \mid (e \text{ po } r)\}$, $rf_4 = rf_3 \cup (w, r)$ and $CF_4 = \{(w', w) \mid w' \in \text{visible}(\tau_3, r, x)\}$ From Lemmas 9 and 10 we get $w \in \text{readable}(\tau_3, r, x)$. We need to show that $CF_4 \subseteq CF_2$. Suppose $e \in CF_4$ e' . We consider the following cases:

- $e \in CF_3$ e' . Since $\tau_3 \sqsubseteq \tau_1$, we have $e \in CF_1$ e' . Since, $\tau_1 \sqsubseteq \tau_2$, we have $e \in CF_2$ e' .
- $e' = w$ and $e \in \text{visible}(\tau_3, r, x)$. That is, we have $e [po_3 \cup rf_3]^+ r$. Since, $\tau_3 \sqsubseteq \tau_1$, we have $e [po_1 \cup rf_1]^+ r$. It follows that $e [po_2 \cup rf_2]^+ r$. Since $\tau_2 \models \text{CCv}$, $w \text{ rf}_2 r$ and CF is total we have $e \in CF_2$ e' .

Lemma 13. *If $\tau_1 \xrightarrow{*}_{\text{Inc}} \tau_2$, $\tau_3 \sqsubseteq \tau_1$ then there exists a τ_4 such that $\tau_3 \xrightarrow{*}_{\text{tr}} \tau_4$ and $\tau_4 \sqsubseteq \tau_2$.*

Proof. Follows from Lemmas 11 and 12.

Lemma 14. $\{\tau \mid (\tau, CF) \in \gamma_{\text{CCv}}^{\text{Inc}}\} \subseteq \{\tau = \mid (\tau, CF) \in \gamma_{\text{CCv}}^{\text{tr}}\}$

Proof. Assume $\tau \in \gamma_{\text{CCv}}^{\text{Inc}}$. We show that there is trace $\tau' \in \gamma_{\text{CCv}}^{\text{tr}}$, such that $\tau' \sqsubseteq \tau$.

Since $\tau \in \gamma_{\text{CCv}}^{\text{Inc}}$, we know that $\tau_\emptyset \xrightarrow{*}_{\text{Inc}} \tau$. That is, there is a sequence $\tau_\emptyset \xrightarrow{\alpha}_{\text{Inc}} \tau_1 \xrightarrow{\alpha}_{\text{Inc}} \tau_2 \cdots \xrightarrow{\alpha}_{\text{Inc}} \tau_n$, where $\tau_\emptyset = \tau_\emptyset$ and $\tau_n = \tau$. Since τ_\emptyset is empty relation, $\tau_\emptyset \models \text{CCv}$. Since we generated traces $\tau_1, \tau_2 \cdots \tau_n$ by following *incremental semantics* transitions from τ_\emptyset , $\tau_1, \tau_2 \cdots \tau_n$ are CCv consistent. From Lemma 13 there is a sequence $\tau'_0 \xrightarrow{\alpha}_{\text{tr}} \tau'_1 \xrightarrow{\alpha}_{\text{tr}} \tau'_2 \cdots \xrightarrow{\alpha}_{\text{tr}} \tau'_n$, where $\tau'_0 = \tau'_0$ and $\tau'_n = \tau'$ such that $\tau_i \sqsubseteq \tau_i$, $i : 1$ to n . Thus we have $\tau'_0 \xrightarrow{\alpha}_{\text{tr}} \tau'$ and $\tau' \sqsubseteq \tau$. Hence, $\tau' \in \gamma_{\text{CCv}}^{\text{tr}}$

From Lemmas 2 to 14, we get following theorem.

Theorem 2. $\{\tau \mid (\tau, CF) \in \gamma_{\text{CCv}}\} = \{\tau = \mid (\tau, CF) \in \gamma_{\text{CCv}}^{\text{tr}}\}$

D Completeness of the DPOR : CCv

We prove the completeness of the DPOR algorithm for CCv. Once again, we use the notation (τ, \mathbf{CF}) to denote the extension $\text{extend}_{\text{CCv}}(\tau)$. We prove that for any CCv consistent trace τ , $\text{EXPLORETRACES}(X, (\tau_0, \emptyset), \epsilon)$ will produce a recursive call $\text{EXPLORETRACES}(X, (\tau', Y'), \pi)$ for some $\tau' = \tau$.

Definition 1 (Trace extension τ extends observation sequence π denoted as $\tau \vdash_{\mathbf{G}} \pi$). For a observation sequence $\pi = \alpha_1 \alpha_2 \cdots \alpha_n$, we define $\tau \vdash_{\mathbf{G}} \pi$ to represent that there is a sequence $\tau_0 \xrightarrow{\alpha_1}_{\text{tr}} \tau_1 \xrightarrow{\alpha_2}_{\text{tr}} \cdots \xrightarrow{\alpha_n}_{\text{tr}} \tau_n$, where $\tau_0 = \tau$.

For $\tau \vdash_{\mathbf{G}} \pi$ we define $\pi(\tau) = \tau_n$. By definition, such τ_n will be unique. We write $\tau \vdash_{\mathbf{Gt}} \pi$ to represent that (i) $\tau \vdash_{\mathbf{G}} \pi$, (ii) $\pi(\tau) = \tau_n$ and τ_n is a complete trace (corresponding to terminating runs).

Definition 2 (*p-free*, *e-free*). For a process $p \in \mathcal{T}$, we say that π is *p-free* if $\pi[i] \notin p$ for all $i : 1$ to n . For an event $e \in p$, we say that π is *e-free* if π is *p-free*.

Definition 3 (Swappable Observables (\sim_{spbl})). For observables α_1 and α_2 , we say that α_1 and α_2 are swappable (denoted as $\alpha_1 \sim_{\text{spbl}} \alpha_2$) to represent that (i) $\alpha_1 \in p$, $\alpha_2 \in p'$ and $p \neq p' \in \mathcal{T}$ (ii) if $\alpha_2 = \text{read}(r, w)$, then $\alpha_1 \neq \text{write}(w)$.

Definition 4 (Swappable Observation Sequences). For observation sequences π_1 and π_2 , we say π_1 and π_2 are swappable (denoted as $\pi_1 \sim_{\text{spbl}} \pi_2$) to represent that $\pi_1 = \pi' \bullet \alpha_1 \bullet \alpha_2 \bullet \pi''$ and $\pi_2 = \pi' \bullet \alpha_2 \bullet \alpha_1 \bullet \pi''$ and $\alpha_1 \sim_{\text{spbl}} \alpha_2$.

$\pi_1 \sim_{\text{spbl}} \pi_2$ represent that we get π_2 by swapping α_1 and α_2 in π_1 . We use \approx_{spbl} to denote the transitive closure of the \sim .

Lemma 15. If $\tau_1 \equiv \tau_2$ and $\tau_1 \vdash_{\mathbf{G}} \pi$ then $\tau_2 \vdash_{\mathbf{G}} \pi$ and $\pi(\tau_1) \equiv \pi(\tau_2)$.

Lemma 16. If $\tau \vdash_{\mathbf{G}} \alpha_1 \bullet \alpha_2$ and $\alpha_1 \sim_{\text{spbl}} \alpha_2$ then $\tau \vdash_{\mathbf{G}} \alpha_2 \bullet \alpha_1$ and $(\alpha_1 \bullet \alpha_2)(\tau) \equiv (\alpha_2 \bullet \alpha_1)(\tau)$.

Proof. Let $\tau = ((E, \mathbf{po}, \mathbf{rf}), \mathbf{CF})$. Consider the following cases.

- $\alpha_1 = \text{write}(w)$, $\alpha_2 = \text{write}(w')$. This is a trivial case. We have $(\alpha_1 \bullet \alpha_2)(\tau) = (\alpha_2 \bullet \alpha_1)(\tau) = ((E', \mathbf{po}', \mathbf{rf}'), \mathbf{CF}')$, where $(E' = E \cup \{w, w'\})$, $\mathbf{po}' = \mathbf{po} \cup \{(e, w) \mid e \in p\} \cup \{(e', w') \mid e' \in p'\}$, $\mathbf{rf}' = \mathbf{rf}$, $\mathbf{CF}' = \mathbf{CF}$.
- $\alpha_1 = \text{write}(w)$, $\alpha_2 = \text{read}(r, w')$. Let $\alpha_1(\tau) = \tau_1$ and $w \in p$, $r \in p$, and $p \neq p' \in \mathcal{T}$. We have $\tau_1 = ((E_1, \mathbf{po}_1, \mathbf{rf}_1), \mathbf{CF}_1)$, where $(E_1 = E \cup w)$, $\mathbf{po}_1 = \mathbf{po} \cup \{(e, w) \mid e \in p\}$. Let $\alpha_2(\tau_1) = \tau_2$. We have $\tau_2 = (E_2, \mathbf{po}_2, \mathbf{rf}_2, \mathbf{CF}_2)$, where $E_2 = E_1 \cup r$, $\mathbf{po}_2 = \mathbf{po}_1 \cup \{(e, r) \mid e \in p'\}$. Since $\tau_1 \vdash_{\mathbf{G}} \alpha_2$, we have $w' \in \text{readable}(\tau_1, r, x)$. Since $p \neq p'$ and $\alpha_1 \sim_{\text{spbl}} \alpha_2$, we have $w' \in \text{readable}(\tau, r, x)$. It follows that $\tau \vdash_{\mathbf{G}} \alpha_2$ and $\text{visible}(\tau_1, r, x) = \text{visible}(\text{CCv}, \tau, r, x)$. Hence, $\tau \vdash_{\mathbf{G}} \alpha_2$. We define $\tau_3 = (E_3, \mathbf{po}_3, \mathbf{rf}_2, \mathbf{CF}_2)$, where $(E_3 = E \cup r)$ and $\mathbf{po}_3 = \mathbf{po} \cup \{(e, r) \mid e \in p'\}$. It follows that $\alpha_2(\tau) = \tau_3$, $\tau_3 \vdash_{\mathbf{G}} \alpha_1$, and $\alpha_1(\tau_3) = \alpha_2(\alpha_1(\tau)) = \tau_2$.

- $\alpha_1 = \text{read}(r, w)$, $\alpha_2 = \text{write}(w')$. Similar to the above case.
- $\alpha_1 = \text{read}(r, w)$, $\alpha_2 = \text{read}(r', w')$ and $r \in p$, $r' \in p'$, and $p \neq p' \in \mathcal{T}$. Let $\tau_1 = \alpha_1(\tau) = ((E_1, \text{po}_1, \text{rf}_1), \text{CF}_1)$. Let $\tau_2 = \alpha_2(\tau_1)$. Since $\tau_1 \vdash_{\mathbb{G}} \alpha_2$, we have $w' \in \text{readable}(\tau_1, r, x)$ and hence $w' \in \text{readable}(\tau, r, x)$. Hence, $\tau \vdash_{\mathbb{G}} \alpha_2$. Let $\tau_3 = \alpha_2(\tau) = (E_3, \text{po}_3, \text{rf}_3, \text{CF}_3)$. Since $\tau \vdash_{\mathbb{G}} \alpha_2$, we have $w \in \text{readable}(\tau, r, x)$. We need to show that $w \in \text{readable}(\tau_3, r, x)$. Assume $w \notin \text{readable}(\tau_3, r, x)$. It follows that there is a $w'' \in \text{visible}(\tau_3, r, x)$ such that $w \text{ CF}_3 w''$. To get $w \text{ CF}_3 w''$, there are two possible cases:
 1. $w \text{ CF} w''$. Since $w'' \in \text{visible}(\tau_3, r', x)$ it follows that $w'' \in \text{visible}(\tau, r', x)$. Since $w \text{ CF} w''$ and $w'' \in \text{visible}(\tau, r', x)$, it follows that $w \notin \text{readable}(\tau, r, x)$. This is a contradiction.
 2. $w' [\text{po} \cup \text{rf} \cup \text{CF}]^+ w''$, $w [\text{po} \cup \text{rf} \cup \text{CF}]^+ w'''$ for some $w''' \in \text{visible}(\tau, r', x)$. Since $w' [\text{po} \cup \text{rf} \cup \text{CF}]^+ w''$, $w [\text{po} \cup \text{rf} \cup \text{CF}]^+ w'''$ it follows that $w' [\text{po}_1 \cup \text{rf}_1 \cup \text{CF}_1]^+ w''$, $w [\text{po}_1 \cup \text{rf}_1 \cup \text{CF}_1]^+ w'''$. Since $w'' \in \text{visible}(\tau, r, x)$ we have $w'' [\text{po}_1 \cup \text{rf}_1 \cup \text{CF}_1]^+ w$ and hence we get $w' [\text{po}_1 \cup \text{rf}_1 \cup \text{CF}_1]^+ w'''$, i.e. $w' \notin \text{readable}(\tau_1, r', x)$. This is a contradiction.

Define $\tau_4 = \alpha_1(\tau_3) = (E_4, \text{po}_4, \text{rf}_4, \text{CF}_4)$

Now consider $w'' \in \text{visible}(\tau_1, r, x)$. Then we have $w'' \text{ CF}_2 w$. To show that $(\alpha_1 \bullet \alpha_2)(\tau) \equiv (\alpha_2 \bullet \alpha_1)(\tau)$, we need to show $w'' \text{ CF}_4 w$. If $w'' \in \text{visible}(\tau_3, r, x)$. Then we have $w'' \text{ CF}_4 w$.

If $w'' \notin \text{visible}(\tau_3, r, x)$, then it means that there is $e \in \text{visible}(\tau, r', x)$ such that $w'' [\text{po} \cup \text{rf} \cup \text{CF}]^+ e$, $e \text{ CF}_3 w'$ and $w' [\text{po} \cup \text{rf} \cup \text{CF}]^+ e'$ for some $e' \in \text{visible}(\tau_3, r, x)$. Since $\tau_4 = \alpha_1(\tau_3)$, $\tau_3 = \alpha_2(\tau)$ and $e' \in \text{visible}(\tau_3, r, x)$, we have $w'' [\text{po}_4 \cup \text{rf}_4 \cup \text{CF}_4]^+ e$, $e \text{ CF}_4 w'$, $w' [\text{po}_4 \cup \text{rf}_4 \cup \text{CF}_4]^+ e'$, and $e' \text{ CF}_4 w$. Hence, we have $w'' \text{ CF}_4 w$.

Similar argument for the case $w'' \in \text{visible}(\tau_2, r', x)$.

Lemma 17. *If $\tau \equiv \tau'$, $\tau \vdash_{\mathbb{G}} \alpha_1 \bullet \alpha_2$ and $\alpha_1 \sim_{\text{spbl}} \alpha_2$ then $\tau' \vdash_{\mathbb{G}} \alpha_2 \bullet \alpha_1$ and $(\alpha_1 \bullet \alpha_2)(\tau) \equiv (\alpha_2 \bullet \alpha_1)(\tau')$.*

Proof. Follows from Lemmas 15 and 27.

From Lemma 17 we have following lemma.

Lemma 18. *If $\tau \equiv \tau'$, $\tau \vdash_{\mathbb{G}} \pi_1 \bullet \pi_2$ and $\pi_1 \sim_{\text{spbl}} \pi_2$ then $\tau' \vdash_{\mathbb{G}} \pi_2 \bullet \pi_1$ and $(\pi_1 \bullet \pi_2)(\tau) \equiv (\pi_2 \bullet \pi_1)(\tau')$.*

Lemma 19. *If $\tau \models_{\text{Gt}} \pi$, $\tau \models_{\mathbb{G}} \text{write}(w)$ and $w \in p$ then $\pi = \pi \bullet \text{write}(w) \bullet \pi''$ for some π' and π'' where π' is p-free.*

Lemma 20. *If $\tau \models_{\text{Gt}} \pi$, $\tau \models_{\mathbb{G}} \text{read}(r, w)$ and $r \in p$ then $\pi = \pi \bullet \text{read}(r, w) \bullet \pi''$ for some π' , π'' and w' where π' is p-free.*

For a observation sequences $\pi = \alpha_1 \alpha_2 \cdots \alpha_n$ and π' we write $\pi \gg_{in} \pi'$ to represent that $\pi' = \pi_0 \bullet \alpha_1 \bullet \pi_1 \bullet \alpha_2 \bullet \pi_2 \cdots \alpha_n \bullet \pi_n$, i.e. π occurs as a non-contiguous sub-word in π' . If $\pi \gg_{in} \pi'$, then we define $\pi' \ominus \pi = \pi_0 \bullet \pi_1 \bullet \pi_2 \cdots \bullet \pi_n$.

Definition 5 (Pre(π, α)). For observation sequence π and observable $\alpha = \pi[i]$, we define $\text{Pre}(\pi, \alpha)$ as the subword π' of π such that (i) $\alpha \in \pi$, (ii) $\pi[j] \in \pi'$ for some $j : 1 \leq j < i$ and there exists $k : j < k \leq i$ such that $\pi[k] \in \pi'$ and $\neg(\pi[j] \sim_{\text{spbl}} \pi[k])$

Lemma 21. If $\pi' = \text{Pre}(\pi, \alpha)$ and $\pi'' = \pi \ominus \pi'$ then $\pi \approx_{\text{spbl}} \pi' \bullet \pi''$.

Lemma 22. If $\pi \approx_{\text{spbl}} \pi' \bullet \pi''$ and $\alpha \in \pi$ then $\text{Pre}(\pi, \alpha) = \text{Pre}(\pi', \alpha)$.

Lemma 23. If $\tau \vdash_{\text{G}} \pi$ then there exists π' such that $\tau \vdash_{\text{Gt}} \pi \bullet \pi'$.

Lemma 24. If $\tau \models \text{CCv}$, $\tau \vdash_{\text{G}} \pi \bullet \alpha$, where $\alpha = \text{read}(r, w^*)$ is observable corresponding to a read event from process p , and π is p -free then there exists write event $w \in E^w$ (can be initialization) such that $\tau \vdash_{\text{G}} \text{read}(r, w) \bullet \pi$.

Proof. Let $\pi = \alpha_1 \alpha_2 \cdots \alpha_n$ and $\tau_0 \xrightarrow{\alpha_1}_{\text{tr}} \tau_1 \xrightarrow{\alpha_2}_{\text{tr}} \tau_2 \cdots \xrightarrow{\alpha_n}_{\text{tr}} \tau_n$, where $\tau_0 = \tau$. Let $\tau_i = (E_i, \text{po}_i, \text{rf}_i, \text{CF}_i)$. Define $w \in E^{w,x}$ such that

- (i) $w \in \text{readable}(\tau_0, r, x)$ and
- (ii) there is no $w' \in \text{visible}(\tau_0, r, x)$ with $w [\text{po}_n \cup \text{rf}_n \cup \text{CF}_n]^+ w'$.

Such a w exists since π is p -free, so all the observables α_i are issued in process other than that of r . Thus, when r is enabled, we can choose any latest write done earlier in τ . We define a sequence of traces $\tau'_0, \tau'_1, \tau'_2 \cdots \tau'_n$ such that

- (I) $\tau_0 \xrightarrow{\text{read}(r,w)}_{\text{tr}} \tau'_0$,
- (II) $\tau'_i \vdash_{\text{G}} \alpha_{i+1}$, and
- (III) $\tau_{i+1} = \alpha_{i+1}(\tau_i)$ for all $i : 0 \leq i < n$.

Define $\text{po} = \{(e, r) \mid e \in p\}$, $\text{rf} = (w, r)$ and $\text{CF} = \{(w', w) \mid w' \in \text{visible}(\tau_0, r, x)\}$

Define $E'_i = E_i \cup r$, $\text{po}'_i = \text{po}_i \cup \text{po}$, $\text{rf}'_i = \text{rf}_i \cup \text{rf}$.

We show that the conditions (II), (III) and (IV) $\text{CF}'_i = \text{CF}_i \cup \text{CF}$ hold inductively. We define CF'_i inductively. Define $\text{CF}'_0 = \text{CF}_0 \cup \text{CF}$ and let CF'_i be the CF relation of $\alpha_i(\tau'_{i-1} = (E'_{i-1}, \text{po}'_{i-1}, \text{rf}'_{i-1}, \text{CF}'_{i-1}))$ for all $i : 1 \leq i < n$. The base case holds trivially.

Inductive Step: Case $\alpha_{i+1} = \text{write}(w')$ is trivial. Suppose $\alpha_{i+1} = \text{rd}(r', w')$, $r' \in p'$ and $r' = \text{read}(r, y)$. If $w' \in \tau$, then the proof is trivial. Assume otherwise. Suppose for the contradiction that $w' \notin \text{readable}(\tau'_i, r', y)$.

Since $w' \notin \text{readable}(\tau'_i, r', y)$ and $w' \in \text{readable}(\tau_i, r', y)$, it follows that there are events $w'' \in \text{visible}(\tau_0, r, x)$ and $w''' \in \text{visible}(\tau_i, r', y)$ such that $w' [\text{po}_i \cup \text{rf}_i \cup \text{CF}_i]^+ w'' \text{CF} w [\text{po}_i \cup \text{rf}_i \cup \text{CF}_i]^+ w'''$. Since $w''' \in \text{visible}(\tau_i, r', y)$, we have $w''' [\text{po}_{i+1} \cup \text{rf}_{i+1} \cup \text{CF}_{i+1}]^+ w'$. That is, we have $w [\text{po}_{i+1} \cup \text{rf}_{i+1} \cup \text{CF}_{i+1}]^+ w''' \text{CF}_{i+1} w' [\text{po}_{i+1} \cup \text{rf}_{i+1} \cup \text{CF}_{i+1}]^+ w''$. Hence, we have $w [\text{po}_n \cup \text{rf}_n \cup \text{CF}_n]^+ w''$. This is a contradiction.

We now show that $\text{CF}'_i = \text{CF}_i \cup \text{CF}$. Assume $e \text{CF}_{i+1} e'$. We show that $e \text{CF}'_{i+1} e'$. If $e \text{CF}_i e'$, then the proof follows from the induction hypothesis. Otherwise, suppose $(e, e') \notin \text{CF}_i$, i.e. $(e, e') \notin \text{CF}'_i$ (This case implies the edge is added

because of $\alpha_{i+1} = \text{read}(r_i, w_i)$ where $e' = w_i$ and $e \in \text{visible}(\tau_i, r_i, x_i)$. Then we have $e'' \in \text{visible}(\tau'_i, r, x)$ such that $e' [po'_i \cup rf'_i \cup CF'_i]^+ e''$. Hence, we have $w_i [po'_i \cup rf'_i \cup CF'_i]^+ e''$. This is a contradiction since $e' = w_i \in \text{readable}(\tau'_i, r_i, x_i)$. Therefore, (II), (III) and (IV) $CF'_i = CF_i \cup CF$ hold.

Definition 6 (Linearization of trace extension). For a trace extension τ and a sequence of observations π , we define π as the linearization of τ if (i) π contains the same events as τ and (ii) events in π are ordered following the relation $(po \cup rf)$.

Definition 7 (Trace extension τ generates π). For the trace extension τ and an observation sequence π , we define that the DPOR algorithm generates π (or simply τ generates π) if some

Lemma 25. If $\tau \vdash_{\text{Gt}} \pi$ then τ will generate π' for some $\pi' \approx_{\text{spbl}} \pi$

Proof. We use induction on $|\pi|$. If τ is the complete trace, then it holds trivially. Assume that $\tau \vdash_{\text{Gt}} \pi$. Consider that τ generates α . α can be either a write event or a read event.

(i) Assume that τ generates $\text{write}(w)$. It follows that $\tau \vdash_{\text{G}} \text{write}(w)$. By Lemma 19, we have $\pi = \pi' \bullet \pi''$ such that π' is w -free. Since π' is w -free it follows that $\pi \approx_{\text{spbl}} w \bullet \pi' \bullet \pi''$, and hence by Lemma 18, it $\tau \vdash_{\text{Gt}} w \bullet \pi' \bullet \pi''$. Hence, there is a trace τ' such that $\tau \xrightarrow{\text{write}(e)}_{\text{tr}} \tau'$ and $\tau' \vdash_{\text{Gt}} \pi' \bullet \pi''$. By the induction hypothesis, it follows that τ' generates $\pi''' \approx_{\text{spbl}} \pi' \bullet \pi''$. Hence, τ generates $w \bullet \pi'''$. The result follows since $\pi \approx_{\text{spbl}} w \bullet \pi'''$.

(ii) Assume that τ generates $\text{read}(r, w^*)$. It follows that $\tau \vdash_{\text{G}} \text{read}(r, w)$. By Lemma 20 we have $\pi = \pi' \bullet \text{read}(r, w) \bullet \pi''$ such that π' is r -clear. We consider the following two cases for w' .

1. $w \in \tau$. This is trivial since the DPOR algorithm will let r to branch on all the possible writes $e \in \text{readable}(\tau, r, x)$ including w .
2. $w \in \pi'$. Let $\pi_1 = \text{Pre}(\pi', w)$. By Lemma 24 we have $\tau \vdash_{\text{G}} \text{read}(r, w') \bullet \pi'$ for some w' . By Lemma 23 we have $\tau \vdash_{\text{Gt}} \text{read}(r, w') \bullet \pi' \bullet \pi_2$ for some π_2 . That is, there exists τ' such that $\tau \xrightarrow{\text{read}(r, w')} \tau'$ and $\tau' \vdash_{\text{Gt}} \pi' \bullet \pi_2$. By the induction hypothesis, for trace τ' DPOR algorithm generates some π_3 such that $\pi_3 \approx_{\text{spbl}} \pi' \bullet \pi_2$. Since $\pi_1 = \text{Pre}(\pi', w)$ and $\pi_3 \approx_{\text{spbl}} \pi' \bullet \pi_2$ by applying Lemma 22 we get $\pi_1 \gg_{\text{in}} \pi_3$. Since π' is r -free, τ generates $\pi_1 \bullet \text{read}(r, w)$. Let $\pi_4 \approx_{\text{spbl}} \pi \ominus (\pi_1 \bullet \text{read}(r, w))$. By applying lemma 21 we get $\pi \approx_{\text{spbl}} \pi_1 \bullet \text{read}(r, w) \bullet \pi_4$. Let $\tau' = (\pi_1 \bullet \text{read}(r, w))(\tau)$. By applying lemma 18 we get $\tau \vdash_{\text{Gt}} \pi_1 \bullet \text{read}(r, w) \bullet \pi_4$. Let $\tau' = (\pi_1 \bullet \text{read}(r, w))(\tau)$, i.e. $\tau' \vdash_{\text{Gt}} \pi_4$. By applying the induction hypothesis, it follows that τ' generates some $\pi_5 \approx_{\text{spbl}} \pi_4$. In other words τ generates $\pi_1 \bullet \text{read}(r, w) \bullet \pi_5$ where $\pi \approx_{\text{spbl}} \pi_1 \bullet \text{read}(r, w) \bullet \pi_5$.

E Details for CC

Soundness If we initiate EXPLORETRACES from the empty trace τ_\emptyset with the empty observation sequence, then all explored traces τ are such that $\tau \models \text{CC}$.

E.1 Completeness

The proof of completeness of DPOR for CC follows the same schema as the completeness proof for CCv . The only difference is in the following lemmas.

Lemma 26. *If $\tau \vdash_{\text{G}} \alpha_1 \bullet \alpha_2$ and $\alpha_1 \sim_{\text{spb1}} \alpha_2$ then $\tau \vdash_{\text{G}} \alpha_2 \bullet \alpha_1$ and $(\alpha_1 \bullet \alpha_2)(\tau) \equiv (\alpha_2 \bullet \alpha_1)(\tau)$.*

Proof. Let $\tau = (E, \text{po}, \text{rf})$. Consider the following cases.

- $\alpha_1 = \text{write}(w)$, $\alpha_2 = \text{write}(w')$. This is a trivial case. We have $(\alpha_1 \bullet \alpha_2)(\tau) = (\alpha_2 \bullet \alpha_1)(\tau) = (E', \text{po}', \text{rf}',)$, where $(E' = (E \cup \{w, w'\}, \text{po}' = \text{po} \cup \{(e, w) \mid e \in p\} \cup \{(e', w') \mid e' \in p'\}, \text{rf}' = \text{rf}$.
 - $\alpha_1 = \text{write}(w)$, $\alpha_2 = \text{read}(r, w')$. Let $\alpha_1(\tau) = \tau_1$ and $w \in p$, $r \in p$, and $p \neq p' \in \mathcal{T}$. We have $\tau_1 = (E_1, \text{po}_1, \text{rf}_1)$, where $(E_1 = E \cup w$, $\text{po}_1 = \text{po} \cup \{(e, w) \mid e \in p\}$. Let $\alpha_2(\tau_1) = \tau_2$. We have $\tau_2 = (E_2, \text{po}_2, \text{rf}_2)$, where $E_2 = E_1 \cup r$, $\text{po}_2 = \text{po}_1 \cup \{(e, r) \mid e \in p'\}$. Since $\tau_1 \vdash_{\text{G}} \alpha_2$, we have $w' \in \text{readable}(\tau_1, r, x)$. Since $p \neq p'$ and $\alpha_1 \sim_{\text{spb1}} \alpha_2$, we have $w' \in \text{readable}(\tau, r, x)$. It follows that $\tau \vdash_{\text{G}} \alpha_2$ and $\text{visible}(\tau_1, r, x) = \text{visible}(\tau, r, x)$. Hence, $\tau \vdash_{\text{G}} \alpha_2$. We define $\tau_3 = (E_3, \text{po}_3, \text{rf}_3)$, where $E_3 = E \cup r$ and $\text{po}_3 = \text{po} \cup \{(e, r) \mid e \in p'\}$. It follows that $\alpha_2(\tau) = \tau_3$, $\tau_3 \vdash_{\text{G}} \alpha_1$, and $\alpha_1(\tau_3) = \alpha_2(\alpha_1(\tau)) = \tau_2$.
 - $\alpha_1 = \text{read}(r, w)$, $\alpha_2 = \text{write}(w')$. Similar to the above case.
 - $\alpha_1 = \text{read}(r, w)$, $\alpha_2 = \text{read}(r', w')$ and $r \in p$, $r' \in p'$, and $p \neq p' \in \mathcal{T}$. Let $\tau_1 = \alpha_1(\tau) = (E_1, \text{po}_1, \text{rf}_1)$. Let $\tau_2 = \alpha_2(\tau_1)$. Since $\tau_1 \vdash_{\text{G}} \alpha_2$, we have $w' \in \text{readable}(\tau_1, r, x)$ and hence $w' \in \text{readable}(\tau, r, x)$. Hence, $\tau \vdash_{\text{G}} \alpha_2$. Let $\tau_3 = \alpha_2(\tau) = (E_3, \text{po}_3, \text{rf}_3)$. Since $\tau \vdash_{\text{G}} \alpha_2$, we have $w \in \text{readable}(\text{CC}, \tau, r, x)$. We need to show that $w \in \text{readable}(\text{CC}, \tau_3, r, x)$. Assume $w \notin \text{readable}(\tau_3, r, x)$. It follows that there is a $w'' \in \text{visible}(\tau_3, r, x)$ such that $w \text{ CO}_3 w''$. To get $w \text{ CO}_3 w''$, there are two possible cases:
 1. $w \text{ CO } w''$. Since $w'' \in \text{visible}(\tau_3, r', x)$ it follows that $w'' \in \text{visible}(\tau, r', x)$. Since $w \text{ CO } w''$ and $w'' \in \text{visible}(\tau, r', x)$, it follows that $w \notin \text{readable}(\tau, r, x)$. This is a contradiction.
 2. $w' \text{ CO}_3 r' \text{ CO } w''$, $w \text{ CO } w'$. This is a contradiction since r' has no successor in po, rf .
- Hence, we have $(\alpha_1 \bullet \alpha_2)(\tau) \equiv (\alpha_2 \bullet \alpha_1)(\tau)$.

Lemma 27. *If $\tau \models \text{CC}$, $\tau \vdash_{\text{G}} \pi \bullet \alpha$, where $\alpha = \text{read}(r, w^*)$ is a observable corresponding to a read event from process p , and π is p -free then there exists write event $w \in \mathcal{W}$ (can be initialization) such that $\tau \vdash_{\text{G}} \text{read}(r, w) \bullet \pi$.*

Proof. Let $\pi = \alpha_1 \alpha_2 \cdots \alpha_n$ and $\tau_0 \xrightarrow{\alpha_1}_{\text{tr}} \tau_1 \xrightarrow{\alpha_2}_{\text{tr}} \tau_2 \cdots \xrightarrow{\alpha_n}_{\text{tr}} \tau_n$, where $\tau_0 = \tau$. Let $\tau_i = (E_i, \text{po}_i, \text{rf}_i)$. Define $w \in \mathcal{W}^x$ such that (i) $w \in \text{readable}(\text{CC}, \tau_0, r, x)$ and (ii) there is no $w' \in \text{visible}(\tau_0, r, x)$ with $w \text{ CO}_n w'$. Such a w exists since π is p -free, so all the observables α_i are issued in process other than that of r . Thus, when r is enabled, we can choose any latest write done earlier in τ . We

define a sequence of traces $\tau'_0, \tau'_1, \tau'_2 \cdots \tau'_n$ such that (I) $\tau_0 \xrightarrow{\text{read}(r,w)}_{\text{tr}} \tau'_0$, (II) $\tau'_i \vdash_{\mathbf{G}} \alpha_{i+1}$, and (III) $\tau_{i+1} = \alpha_{i+1}(\tau_i)$ for all $i : 0 \leq i < n$.

Define $\text{po} = \{(e, r) \mid e \in p\}$, $\text{rf} = (w, r)$.

Define $E'_i = E_i \cup r$, $\text{po}'_i = \text{po}_i \cup \text{po}$, $\text{rf}'_i = \text{rf}_i \cup \text{rf}$.

We show that conditions (II), and (III) hold inductively. The base case holds trivially.

Inductive Step: Case $\alpha_{i+1} = \text{write}(w')$ is trivial. Suppose $\alpha_{i+1} = \text{rd}(r', w')$, $r' \in p'$ and $r' = \text{read}(r, y)$. If $w' \in \tau$, then the proof is trivial. Assume otherwise. Suppose for the contradiction that $w' \notin \text{readable}(\tau'_i, r', y)$.

Since $w' \notin \text{readable}(\tau'_i, r', y)$ and $w' \in \text{readable}(\tau_i, r', y)$, it follows that there is event $w'' \in \text{visible}(\tau_i, r', y)$ such that $w' \text{ CO}_i w \text{ rf}'_i r \text{ CO}_i w''$. This is a contradiction since r' has no successor in po, rf . Therefore, (II), and (III) holds.

F Details for CM

F.1 Properties of Trace semantics for CM

Here as well, we follow the notation $(\langle \mathbf{E}, \text{po}, \text{rf} \rangle, \mathbf{HB})$ for an extended trace τ instead of $\text{extend}_{\text{CM}}(\tau)$.

Lemma 28. *For extended traces $\tau_{\text{CM}}^1 = \text{extend}_{\text{CM}}(\tau^1)$ and $\tau_{\text{CM}}^2 = \text{extend}_{\text{CM}}(\tau^2)$ if $\tau_{\text{CM}}^1 \xrightarrow{\text{read}(r,w)}_{\text{tr}} \tau_{\text{CM}}^2$ and $\tau^1 \models \text{CM}$, then $\tau^2 \models \text{CM}$.*

Proof. Let $\tau_1 = (\langle E, \text{po}_1, \text{rf}_1 \rangle, \mathbf{HB}_1)$ and $\tau_2 = (\langle E', \text{po}_2, \text{rf}_2 \rangle, \mathbf{HB}_2)$. Let e be the read event and let $e' \in \text{readable}(\tau, e, x)$ be the chosen write event that e reads from, while $\tau_1 \xrightarrow{\text{read}(r,w)}_{\text{tr}} \tau_2$. For process p , let $\mathbf{HB}_{1p}, \mathbf{HB}_{2p}$ respectively denote the process p ordering in $\mathbf{HB}_1, \mathbf{HB}_2$ respectively.

Then, $\text{rf}'_2 = \text{rf}'_1 \cup (e', e)$ and

$$\mathbf{HB}_2 = \mathbf{HB}_{2p} \cup \left(\bigcup_{p': p_1 - p_n, p' \neq p} \mathbf{HB}_{2p'} \right)$$

where $\mathbf{HB}_{2p'} = \mathbf{HB}_{1p'} \cup \{(e, r) \mid (e \text{ po } r)\} \cup (w, r)$ and $\mathbf{HB}_{2p} = [\mathbf{HB}_{1p} \cup \mathbf{HB}_p']^+$ and \mathbf{HB}_p' is computed as follows:

- (i) Initially, $\mathbf{HB}_p' = \{(e'', e') \mid e'' \in \text{visible}(\tau, r, x)\}$.
- (ii) Then, for all events e_r, e_w and e'_w if $e_r \in p$, $e_w \text{ rf } e_r$ and $e_w [\mathbf{HB}_{1p}; \mathbf{HB}_p']^+ e'_w$ then $\mathbf{HB}_p' = \mathbf{HB}_p' \cup (e_r, e'_w)$.

First, we prove the following.

- (i) there are events e_1, e_2 and e_3 such that $e_1 \mathbf{HB}_{2p} e_3$ and $e_2 \text{ rf}'_2 e_3$. Then we show that $e_1 \mathbf{HB}_{2p} e_2$.
- (ii) there are events e_1, e_2 and e_3 such that $e_1 \mathbf{HB}_{2p} e_2$ and $e_1 \text{ rf}'_2 e_3$.

Then we show that $e_3 \mathbf{HB}_{2p} e_2$. For case (i): Since e has no successor in $[\text{po} \cup \text{rf}]^+$, we need to consider only process p and $e_3 \text{ po}_1 e$ with the following scenario.

★ $y = x$, $e_3 = e$, $e_2 = e'$ and there is a event $e_4 \in \text{visible}(\tau, r, x)$ such that $e_1 \text{HB}_{1p} e_4$. By definition of $\tau_1 \xrightarrow{\text{read}(r,w)}_{\text{tr}} \tau_2$, we have $e_4 \text{HB}_{2p} e'$. Hence, it follows that $e_1 \text{HB}_{2p} e_2$.

Case (ii) follows from step(ii) of computing HB_p' .

Suppose that $\tau_2 \not\models \text{CM}$. That means there is CMcycle caused by HB_{2p} . Since, $\tau_1 \models \text{CM}$ we consider two cases:

- $e' \text{HB}_{2p} e''$ for some $e'' \in \text{visible}(\tau_1, r, x)$. This contradicts the fact that $e' \in \text{readable}(\tau_1, e, x)$.
- For some $e_r \text{po}_1 e$, and $e_w, e'_w \in \mathcal{W}^y$, $e_w \text{rf}_1 e_r$ we have cycle of form $e_r \text{HB}_{2p} e'_w \text{HB}_{1p} e_r$.
Since $e'_w \text{HB}_{1p} e_r$, we have $e'_w \in \text{visible}(\tau_1, e_r, x)$ and $e'_w \text{HB}_{1p} e_w$. We added relation $e_r \text{HB}_{2p} e'_w$ because we observed $e_w \text{HB}_{2p} e'_w$ which was not present in HB_{1p} . It follows there is a event $e'' \in \text{visible}(\tau_1, e, x)$ such that $e_w \text{HB}_{1p} e''$, $e' \text{HB}_{1p} e'_w$. Since $e_w \text{HB}_{1p} e''$, $e' \text{HB}_{1p} e'_w$ and $e'_w \text{HB}_{1p} e_w$, we have $e' \notin \text{readable}(\tau_1, e, x)$. This is a contradiction.

Lemma 29. *For extended traces $\tau_{\text{CM}}^1 = \text{extend}_{\text{CM}}(\tau^1)$ and $\tau_{\text{CM}}^2 = \text{extend}_{\text{CM}}(\tau^2)$ if $\tau_{\text{CM}}^1 \xrightarrow{\text{write}(w)}_{\text{tr}} \tau_{\text{CM}}^2$ and $\tau^1 \models \text{CM}$, then $\tau^2 \models \text{CM}$.*

Proof. The proof follows from the definition of $\xrightarrow{\text{write}(w)}_{\text{tr}}$.

F.2 CM DPOR Soundness Proof

As in the case of CCv, we first define a new semantics called *incremental semantics*.

CM incremental semantics We define a new *incremental semantics* for CM. In *incremental semantics* each trace gives the total order of the write events per variable for each process. To define the semantics we introduce notation $\xrightarrow{\alpha}_{\text{Inc}}$ on traces.

- Transition $\tau_1 \xrightarrow{\text{write}(w)}_{\text{Inc}} \tau_2$ where $w \in p$ is write event, $\tau_1 = (E, \text{po}_1, \text{rf}_1, \text{HB}_1)$, $\tau_2 = (E', \text{po}_2, \text{rf}_2, \text{HB}_2)$, $E' = E \cup \{w\}$, $\text{po}_2 = \text{po}_1 \cup (epow)$, $\text{rf}_2 = \text{rf}_1$, $\text{HB}_1 \subseteq \text{HB}_2$ and HB_2 gives total order over all write event per process, i.e $\text{HB}_2 = \bigcup_{p:p_1-p_n} \text{HB}_{2p}$ and HB_{2p} gives total order between all events $e \in E^{\text{wt}} \cup \{e' \mid e' \in p\}$.
- Transition $\tau_1 \xrightarrow{\text{read}(r,w)}_{\text{Inc}} \tau_2$ where $r \in p$ is event reading from w , $\tau_1 = (E, \text{po}_1, \text{rf}_1, \text{HB}_1)$, $E' = E \cup r$, $\tau_2 = (E', \text{po}_2, \text{rf}_2, \text{HB}_2)$, $\text{po}_2 = \text{po}_1 \cup (e \text{po} r)$, $\text{rf}_2 = \text{rf}_1 \cup (w, r)$, $\text{HB}_2 = \text{HB}_1$.
In this transition, $r \in p$ reads from the last write w in the total order for process p.

We define $\gamma^{\text{Inc}} = \{\tau \mid \tau_\emptyset \rightarrow_{\text{Inc}} \tau\}$ as the set of traces $\tau = ((E, \text{po}, \text{rf}), \text{HB})$ for the given program obtained by starting from the configurations γ and empty

trace τ_\emptyset . We define $\gamma_{\text{CM}}^{\text{Inc}} := \{\tau \in \gamma^{\text{Inc}} \mid \tau \models \text{CM}\}$, i.e. $\gamma_{\text{CM}}^{\text{Inc}}$ is set of CM consistent trace extensions generated using *incremental semantics*.

We define $\gamma^{\text{tr}} = \{\tau \mid \tau_\emptyset \rightarrow_{\text{tr}} \tau\}$ as the set of trace extensions $\tau = ((E, \text{po}, \text{rf}), \text{HB})$ for the given program obtained by starting from the empty trace τ_\emptyset and configuration γ . We define $\gamma_{\text{CM}}^{\text{tr}} := \{\tau \in \gamma^{\text{tr}} \mid \tau \models \text{CM}\}$, i.e. $\gamma_{\text{CM}}^{\text{tr}}$ is set of CM consistent traces generated using *trace semantics*.

Recall that $\gamma_{\text{CM}} := \{\tau_{\text{CM}} \mid \exists \rho \text{Runs}(\gamma). \rho \models \tau_{\text{CM}} \wedge \tau_{\text{CM}} \models \text{CM}\}$ is set of traces generated under CM from a given configuration γ .

Lemma 30. $\gamma_{\text{CM}}^{\text{Inc}} = \gamma_{\text{CM}}$.

We prove the soundness of CM DPOR in two parts: (I) $\{\tau \mid (\tau, \text{HB}) \in \gamma_{\text{CM}}^{\text{tr}}\} \subseteq \{\tau \mid (\tau, \text{HB}) \in \gamma_{\text{CM}}^{\text{Inc}}\}$ and (II) $\{\tau \mid (\tau, \text{HB}) \in \gamma_{\text{CM}}^{\text{Inc}}\} \subseteq \{\tau \mid (\tau, \text{HB}) \in \gamma_{\text{CM}}^{\text{tr}}\}$.

F.3 $\{\tau \mid (\tau, \text{HB}) \in \gamma_{\text{CM}}^{\text{tr}}\} \subseteq \{\tau \mid (\tau, \text{HB}) \in \gamma_{\text{CM}}^{\text{Inc}}\}$

Lemma 31. *If $\tau_1 \xrightarrow{\text{write}(w)}_{\text{tr}} \tau_2$, $\tau_2 \sqsubseteq \tau_4$, and τ_4 gives total order of write events for each process then there exists a τ_3 such that $\tau_3 \xrightarrow{\text{write}(w)}_{\text{Inc}} \tau_4$ and $\tau_1 \sqsubseteq \tau_3$.*

Proof. Let $\tau_1 = ((E_1, \text{po}_1, \text{rf}_1), \text{HB}_1)$, $\tau_2 = ((E_2, \text{po}_2, \text{rf}_2), \text{HB}_2)$ and $\tau_4 = ((E_4, \text{po}_4, \text{rf}_4), \text{HB}_4)$. Since $\tau_2 \sqsubseteq \tau_4$, we have $\text{po}_2 = \text{po}_4$, $\text{rf}_4 = \text{rf}_2$ and $\text{HB}_2 \sqsubseteq \text{HB}_4$. We have $E_2 = E_1 \cup w$, $\text{po}_2 = \text{po}_1 \cup \{e \text{po} w\}$, $\text{rf}_2 = \text{rf}_1$ and $\text{HB}_1 = \text{HB}_2$.

Define $\tau_3 = (E_3, \text{po}_3, \text{rf}_3, \text{HB}_3)$ where $E_3 = E_1$, $\text{rf}_3 = \text{rf}_1 = \text{rf}_4|_{E_3}$ and $\text{HB}_3 = \text{HB}_4|_{E_3}$. It follows that $\tau_3 \xrightarrow{\text{write}(w)}_{\text{Inc}} \tau_4$. We need to show that $\text{HB}_1 \subseteq \text{HB}_3$. Consider $e \in \text{HB}_{1p}$ e' . Since $\text{HB}_1 \subseteq \text{HB}_2$ and $\text{HB}_2 \subseteq \text{HB}_4$. Since $e, e' \in E_1 = E_3$ and $\text{HB}_3 = \text{HB}_4|_{E_3}$, we have $e \in \text{HB}_3$ e' .

Lemma 32. *If $\tau_1 \xrightarrow{\text{read}(r,w)}_{\text{tr}} \tau_2$, $\tau_2 \sqsubseteq \tau_4$, and τ_4 gives total order of write events for each process then there exists a τ_3 such that $\tau_3 \xrightarrow{\text{read}(r,w)}_{\text{Inc}} \tau_4$ and $\tau_1 \sqsubseteq \tau_3$.*

Proof. Let $\tau_1 = ((E_1, \text{po}_1, \text{rf}_1), \text{HB}_1)$, $\tau_2 = ((E_2, \text{po}_2, \text{rf}_2), \text{HB}_2)$ and $\tau_4 = ((E_4, \text{po}_4, \text{rf}_4), \text{HB}_4)$. Since $\tau_2 \sqsubseteq \tau_4$, we have $\text{po}_2 = \text{po}_4$, $\text{rf}_4 = \text{rf}_2$ and $\text{HB}_2 \sqsubseteq \text{HB}_4$. We have $E_2 = E_1 \cup r$, $\text{po}_2 = \text{po}_1 \cup \{e \text{po} r\}$, $\text{rf}_2 = \text{rf}_1 \cup (w, r)$ and

$$\text{HB}_2 = \text{HB}_{2p} \cup \left(\bigcup_{p': p_1 - p_n, p' \neq p} \text{HB}_{2p'} \right)$$

where $\text{HB}_{2p'} = \text{HB}_{1p'} \cup \{(e, r) \mid (e \text{po} r)\} \cup (w, r)$ and $\text{HB}_{2p} = [\text{HB}_{1p} \cup \text{HB}_p']^+$ and HB_p' is computed as follows:

- (i) Initially, $\text{HB}_p' = \{(e'', e') \mid e'' \in \text{visible}(\tau, r, x)\}$.
- (ii) Then, for all events e_r , e_w and e'_w if $e_r \in p$, $e_w \text{rf} e_r$ and $e_w \in [\text{HB}_{1p}; \text{HB}_p']^+$ e'_w then $\text{HB}_p' = \text{HB}_p' \cup (e_r, e'_w)$.

Define $\tau_3 = ((E_3, po_3, rf_3), HB_3)$ where $E_3 = E_1$, $rf_3 = rf_1 = rf_1|_{E_3}$ and $HB_3 = HB_4|_{E_3}$. It follows that $\tau_3 \xrightarrow{read(r,w)}_{\text{Inc}} \tau_4$. We need to show that $HB_1 \subseteq HB_3$. Consider $e \in HB_{1p}$. Since $HB_1 \subseteq HB_2$ and $HB_2 \subseteq HB_4$. Since $e, e' \in E_1 = E_3$ and $HB_3 = HB_4|_{E_3}$, we have $e \in HB_3$.

Lemma 33. *If $\tau_1 \xrightarrow{*}_{\text{tr}} \tau_2$, $\tau_2 \sqsubseteq \tau_4$ and τ_4 gives total order of write events for each process then there exists a τ_3 such that $\tau_3 \xrightarrow{*}_{\text{Inc}} \tau_4$ and $\tau_1 \sqsubseteq \tau_3$.*

Proof. Follows from Lemmas 31 and 32.

Lemma 34. $\{\tau \mid (\tau, HB) \in \gamma_{\text{CM}}^{\text{tr}}\} \subseteq \{\tau \mid (\tau, HB) \in \gamma_{\text{CM}}^{\text{Inc}}\}$

Proof. Assume $\tau \in \gamma_{\text{CM}}^{\text{tr}}$. We show that there is trace $\tau' \in \gamma_{\text{CM}}^{\text{Inc}}$, such that $\tau \sqsubseteq \tau'$.

Since $\tau \in \gamma_{\text{CM}}^{\text{tr}}$, we know that $\tau_0 \xrightarrow{*}_{\text{tr}} \tau$. That is, there is a sequence $\tau_0 \xrightarrow{\alpha}_{\text{tr}} \tau_1 \xrightarrow{\alpha}_{\text{tr}} \tau_2 \cdots \xrightarrow{\alpha}_{\text{tr}} \tau_n$, where $\tau_0 = \tau_0$ and $\tau_n = \tau$. Since τ_0 is empty relation it follows that $\tau_0 \models \text{CM}$. Since we generated traces $\tau_1, \tau_2 \cdots \tau_n$ by following *trace semantics* transitions from τ_0 , $\tau_1, \tau_2 \cdots \tau_n$ are CM consistent. From Lemma 33 there is a sequence $\tau'_0 \xrightarrow{\alpha}_{\text{Inc}} \tau'_1 \xrightarrow{\alpha}_{\text{Inc}} \tau'_2 \cdots \xrightarrow{\alpha}_{\text{Inc}} \tau'_n$, where $\tau'_0 = \tau_0$ and $\tau'_n = \tau$ such that $\tau_i \sqsubseteq \tau'_i$, $i : 1$ to n . Thus we have $\tau'_0 \xrightarrow{*}_{\text{Inc}} \tau'$ and $\tau \sqsubseteq \tau'$. Hence, $\tau' \in \gamma_{\text{CM}}^{\text{Inc}}$

F.4 $\{\tau \mid (\tau, HB) \in \gamma_{\text{CM}}^{\text{Inc}}\} \subseteq \{\tau \mid (\tau, HB) \in \gamma_{\text{CM}}^{\text{tr}}\}$

Lemma 35. $\tau_1 \xrightarrow{read(r,w)}_{\text{Inc}}$ and $\tau_2 \models \text{CM}$, then $w \in \text{readable}(\tau_1, r, x)$.

Proof. Let $\tau_1 = ((E_1, po_1, rf_1), HB_1)$, $\tau_2 = ((E_2, po_2, rf_2), HB_2)$ and let $r \in p$. Assume $w \notin \text{readable}(\tau_1, r, x)$. That means, there is an event $e \in E^{\text{wt}, x}$ such that $w \in [HB_{1p}]^+ e$ and $e \in HB_{1p} r$. Since HB_{1p} gives the total order for write events on the same variable, if $e \in HB_{1p} w$, then we get $e \in HB_{1p} w \in [HB_p]_1^+ e$. This is a contradiction to the fact that $\tau_2 \models \text{CM}$. If $w \in HB_{1p} e$, since $w \in rf r$, by definition of HB_2 we add an HB_{2p} edge from e to w , creating a cycle $w \in HB_{2p} e \in HB_{2p} w$. This is a contradiction to the fact that $\tau_2 \models \text{CM}$.

Lemma 36. *If $\tau_1 \sqsubseteq \tau_2$ and $w \in \text{readable}(\tau_2, r, x)$ then $w \in \text{readable}(\tau_1, r, x)$.*

Proof. Since $w \in \text{readable}(\tau_2, r, x)$, there is no write event such that $w \in [HB_{2p}]^+ e \in HB_{2p} r$. Since $\tau_1 \sqsubseteq \tau_2$, we have $HB_{1p} \subseteq HB_{2p}$. Hence, there is no write event e such that $w \in [HB_{1p}]^+ e \in HB_{1p} r$. Therefore, $w \in \text{readable}(\tau_1, r, x)$.

Lemma 37. *If $\tau_1 \xrightarrow{write(w)}_{\text{Inc}} \tau_2$, and $\tau_3 \sqsubseteq \tau_1$, then there exists $\tau_4 \xrightarrow{write(w)}_{\text{tr}} \tau_4$ and $\tau_4 \sqsubseteq \tau_2$.*

Proof. Let $\tau_1 = ((E_1, po_1, rf_1), HB_1)$, $\tau_2 = ((E_2, po_2, rf_2), HB_2)$ and $\tau_3 = ((E_3, po_3, rf_3), HB_3)$. Since $\tau_3 \sqsubseteq \tau_1$, we have $po_3 = po_1$, $rf_3 = rf_1$ and $HB_3 \subseteq HB_1$. We have $E_2 = E_1 \cup \{w\}$, $po_2 = po_1 \cup \{(e, w) \mid (epow)\}$, $rf_2 = rf_1$ and $HB_1 \subseteq HB_2$ and HB_2 gives total order on write events.

Define $\tau_4 = (E_4, \mathit{po}_4, \mathit{rf}_4, \mathit{HB}_4)$ where $E_4 = E_3 \cup w$, $\mathit{po}_4 = \mathit{po}_3 \cup \{(e, w) \mid (epow)\}$, $\mathit{rf}_4 = \mathit{rf}_3 \cup (w, r)$ and $\mathit{HB}_4 = \mathit{HB}_3$. It follows that $\tau_3 \xrightarrow{\text{write}(w)}_{\text{tr}} \tau_4$. Since $\mathit{HB}_3 \subseteq \mathit{HB}_1 \subseteq \mathit{HB}_2$, we have $\mathit{HB}_4 \subseteq \mathit{HB}_2$. Hence, $\tau_4 \sqsubseteq \tau_2$.

Lemma 38. *If $\tau_1 \xrightarrow{\text{read}(r,w)}_{\text{Inc}} \tau_2$, and $\tau_3 \sqsubseteq \tau_1$, then there exists $\tau_3 \xrightarrow{\text{read}(r,w)}_{\text{tr}} \tau_4$ and $\tau_4 \sqsubseteq \tau_2$.*

Proof. Let $\tau_1 = ((E_1, \mathit{po}_1, \mathit{rf}_1), \mathit{HB}_1)$, $\tau_2 = ((E_2, \mathit{po}_2, \mathit{rf}_2), \mathit{HB}_2)$ and $\tau_3 = ((E_3, \mathit{po}_3, \mathit{rf}_3), \mathit{HB}_3)$. Since $\tau_3 \sqsubseteq \tau_1$, we have $\mathit{po}_3 = \mathit{po}_1$, $\mathit{rf}_3 = \mathit{rf}_1$ and $\mathit{HB}_3 \subseteq \mathit{HB}_1$. We have $E_2 = E_1 \cup \{r\}$, $\mathit{po}_2 = \mathit{po}_1 \cup \{(e, r) \mid (epor)\}$, $\mathit{rf}_2 = \mathit{rf}_1 \cup (w, r)$ and $\mathit{HB}_1 \subseteq \mathit{HB}_2$ and HB_2 gives total order on write events.

Define $\tau_4 = (E_4, \mathit{po}_4, \mathit{rf}_4, \mathit{HB}_4)$ where $E_4 = E_3 \cup r$, $\mathit{po}_4 = \mathit{po}_3 \cup \{(e, r) \mid (epor)\}$, $\mathit{rf}_4 = \mathit{rf}_3 \cup (w, r)$ and

$$\mathit{HB}_4 = \mathit{HB}_{4p} \cup \left(\bigcup_{p': p_1 - p_n, p' \neq p} \mathit{HB}_{4p'} \right)$$

where $\mathit{HB}_{4p'} = \mathit{HB}_{3p'} \cup \{(e, r) \mid (e \mathit{po} r)\} \cup (w, r)$ and $\mathit{HB}_{4p} = [\mathit{HB}_{3p} \cup \mathit{HB}_p]^+$ and HB_p' is computed as follows:

- (i) Initially, $\mathit{HB}_p' = \{(e'', e') \mid e'' \in \text{visible}(\tau, r, x)\}$.
- (ii) Then, for all events e_r, e_w and e'_w if $e_r \in p$, $e_w \mathit{rf} e_r$ and $e_w [\mathit{HB}_{3p}; \mathit{HB}_p']^+ e'_w$ then $\mathit{HB}_p' = \mathit{HB}_p' \cup (e_r, e'_w)$.

From Lemmas 35 and 36 we get $w \in \text{readable}(\tau_3, r, x)$. We need to show that $\mathit{HB}_4 \subseteq \mathit{HB}_2$. Suppose $e \mathit{HB}_{4p} e'$. We consider the following cases:

- $e \mathit{HB}_{3p} e'$. That is, we have $e \mathit{HB}_{1p} e'$. Since, $\tau_1 \sqsubseteq \tau_2$, we have $e \mathit{HB}_{2p} e'$.
- $e' = w$ and $e \in \text{visible}(\tau_3, r, x)$. That is, we have $e \mathit{HB}_{3p} r$. Since, $\tau_3 \sqsubseteq \tau_1$, we have $e \mathit{HB}_{1p} r$. It follows that $e \mathit{HB}_{2p} r$. Since $\tau_2 \models \text{CM}$ and $w \mathit{rf}_2 r$, we have $e \mathit{HB}_{2p} e'$.
- $e' \mathit{po}_3 r$, $e_w \mathit{rf}_3 e'$, and $e_w \mathit{HB}_{4p} e'$ because of step (ii) of saturation in $\tau_3 \xrightarrow{\text{read}(r,w)}_{\text{tr}} \tau_4$. Since $\tau_3 \sqsubseteq \tau_1 \sqsubseteq \tau_2$, we have $e' \mathit{po}_2 r$, $e_w \mathit{rf}_2 e'$. Since HB_{2p} gives total order between all events $e \in \mathcal{W} \cup \{e' \mid e' \in p\}$ and $\tau_2 \models \text{CM}$, we have $e \mathit{HB}_{2p} e'$.

Lemma 39. *If $\tau_1 \xrightarrow{*}_{\text{Inc}} \tau_2$, $\tau_3 \sqsubseteq \tau_1$ then there exists a τ_4 such that $\tau_3 \xrightarrow{*}_{\text{tr}} \tau_4$ and $\tau_4 \sqsubseteq \tau_2$.*

Proof. Follows from Lemmas 37 and 38.

Lemma 40. $\{\tau \mid (\tau, \mathit{HB}) \in \gamma_{\text{CM}}^{\text{Inc}}\} \subseteq \{\tau \mid (\tau, \mathit{HB}) \in \gamma_{\text{CM}}^{\text{tr}}\}$

Proof. Assume $\tau \in \gamma_{\text{CM}}^{\text{Inc}}$. We show that there is trace $\tau' \in \gamma_{\text{CM}}^{\text{tr}}$, such that $\tau' \sqsubseteq \tau$.

Since $\tau \in \gamma_{\text{CM}}^{\text{Inc}}$, we know that $\tau_0 \xrightarrow{*}_{\text{Inc}} \tau$. That is, there is a sequence $\tau_0 \xrightarrow{\alpha}_{\text{Inc}} \tau_1 \xrightarrow{\alpha}_{\text{Inc}} \tau_2 \cdots \xrightarrow{\alpha}_{\text{Inc}} \tau_n$, where $\tau_0 = \tau_0$ and $\tau_n = \tau$. Since τ_0 is empty relation, it follows that $\tau_0 \models \text{CM}$. Since we generated traces $\tau_1, \tau_2 \cdots \tau_n$ by following *incremental semantics* transitions from $\tau_0, \tau_1, \tau_2 \cdots \tau_n$ are CM consistent. From

Lemma 39 there is a sequence $\tau'_0 \xrightarrow{\alpha} \tau'_1 \xrightarrow{\alpha} \tau'_2 \cdots \xrightarrow{\alpha} \tau'_n$, where $\tau'_0 = \tau'_\emptyset$ and $\tau'_n = \tau'$ such that $\tau_i \sqsubseteq \tau'_i$, $i : 1$ to n . Thus we have $\tau'_\emptyset \xrightarrow{\alpha} \tau'$ and $\tau' \sqsubseteq \tau$. Hence, $\tau' \in \gamma_{\text{CM}}^{\text{tr}}$

From Lemmas 28 to 40, we get following theorem.

Theorem 3. $\{\tau \mid (\tau, \text{HB}) \in \gamma_{\text{CM}}\} = \{\tau \mid (\tau, \text{HB}) \in \gamma_{\text{CM}}^{\text{tr}}\}$

F.5 Completeness

We prove the completeness of the DPOR algorithm. Once again, we use the notation (τ, HB) to denote the extension $\text{extend}_{\text{CM}}(\tau)$. We prove that for any CM consistent trace τ , $\text{EXPLORETRACES}(X, (\tau_\emptyset, \emptyset), \epsilon)$ will produce a recursive call $\text{EXPLORETRACES}(X, (\tau', Y'), \pi)$ for some $\tau' = \tau$.

Definition 8 (Trace extension τ extends observation sequence π denoted as $\tau \vdash_{\text{G}} \pi$). For a observation sequence $\pi = \alpha_1 \alpha_2 \cdots \alpha_n$, we define $\tau \vdash_{\text{G}} \pi$ to represent that there is a sequence $\tau_0 \xrightarrow{\alpha_1} \tau_1 \xrightarrow{\alpha_2} \cdots \xrightarrow{\alpha_n} \tau_n$, where $\tau_0 = \tau$.

For $\tau \vdash_{\text{G}} \pi$ such we define $\pi(\tau) = \tau_n$. By definition, such τ_n will be unique. We write $\tau \vdash_{\text{Gt}} \pi$ to represent that (i) $\tau \vdash_{\text{G}} \pi$, (ii) $\pi(\tau) = \tau_n$ and τ_n is complete trace.

Definition 9 (p-free , e-free). For a process $p \in \mathcal{T}$, we say that π is p-free if $\pi[i] \notin p$ for all $i : 1$ to n . For an event $e \in p$, we say that π is e-free if π is p-free.

Definition 10 (Swappable Observables (\sim_{spb1})). For observables α_1 and α_2 , we say that α_1 and α_2 are swappable (denoted as $\alpha_1 \sim_{\text{spb1}} \alpha_2$) to represent that (i) $\alpha_1 \in p$, $\alpha_2 \in p'$ and $p \neq p' \in \mathcal{T}$ (ii) if $\alpha_2 = \text{read}(r, w)$, then $\alpha_1 \neq \text{write}(w)$.

Definition 11 (Swappable Observation Sequences). For a observation sequences π_1 and π_2 , we say π_1 and π_2 are swappable (denoted as $\pi_1 \sim_{\text{spb1}} \pi_2$) to represent that $\pi_1 = \pi' \bullet \alpha_1 \bullet \alpha_2 \bullet \pi''$ and $\pi_2 = \pi' \bullet \alpha_2 \bullet \alpha_1 \bullet \pi''$ and $\alpha_1 \sim_{\text{spb1}} \alpha_2$.

$\pi_1 \sim_{\text{spb1}} \pi_2$ represent that we get π_2 by swapping α_1 and α_2 in π_1 . We use \approx_{spb1} to denote the transitive closure of the \sim .

Lemma 41. If $\tau_1 \equiv \tau_2$ and $\tau_1 \vdash_{\text{G}} \pi$ then $\tau_2 \vdash_{\text{G}} \pi$ and $\pi(\tau_1) \equiv \pi(\tau_2)$.

Lemma 42. If $\tau \vdash_{\text{G}} \alpha_1 \bullet \alpha_2$ and $\alpha_1 \sim_{\text{spb1}} \alpha_2$ then $\tau \vdash_{\text{G}} \alpha_2 \bullet \alpha_1$ and $(\alpha_1 \bullet \alpha_2)(\tau) \equiv (\alpha_2 \bullet \alpha_1)(\tau)$.

Proof. Let $\tau = ((E, \text{po}, \text{rf}), \text{HB})$. Consider the following cases.

- $\alpha_1 = \text{write}(w)$, $\alpha_2 = \text{write}(w')$. This is a trivial case. We have $(\alpha_1 \bullet \alpha_2)(\tau) = (\alpha_2 \bullet \alpha_1)(\tau) = (E', \text{po}', \text{rf}', \text{HB}')$, where $E' = E \cup \{w, w'\}$, $\text{po}' = \text{po} \cup \{(e, w) \mid e \in p\} \cup \{(e', w') \mid e' \in p'\}$, $\text{rf}' = \text{rf}$, $\text{HB}' = \text{HB}$.

- $\alpha_1 = \text{write}(w)$, $\alpha_2 = \text{read}(r, w')$. Let $\alpha_1(\tau) = \tau_1$ and $w \in p$ $r \in p$, and $p \neq p' \in \mathcal{T}$. We have $\tau_1 = (E_1, \text{po}_1, \text{rf}, \text{HB})$, where $E_1 = E \cup w$, $\text{po}_1 = \text{po} \cup \{(e, w) \mid e \in p\}$. Let $\alpha_2(\tau_1) = \tau_2$. We have $\tau_2 = (E_2, \text{po}_2, \text{rf}_2, \text{HB}_2)$, where $E_2 = E_1 \cup r$, $\text{po}_2 = \text{po}_1 \cup \{(e, r) \mid e \in p'\}$. Since $\tau_1 \vdash_{\text{G}} \alpha_2$, we have $w' \in \text{readable}(\tau_1, r, x)$. Since $p \neq p'$ and $\alpha_1 \sim_{\text{spb1}} \alpha_2$, we have $w' \in \text{readable}(\tau, r, x)$. It follows that $\tau \vdash_{\text{G}} \alpha_2$ and $\text{visible}(\tau_1, r, x) = \text{visible}(\tau, r, x)$. Hence, $\tau \vdash_{\text{G}} \alpha_2$. We define $\tau_3 = (E_3, \text{po}_3, \text{rf}_3, \text{HB}_3)$, where $E_3 = E \cup r$ and $\text{po}_3 = \text{po} \cup \{(e, r) \mid e \in p'\}$. It follows that $\alpha_2(\tau) = \tau_3$, $\tau_3 \vdash_{\text{G}} \alpha_1$, and $\alpha_1(\tau_3) = \alpha_2(\alpha_1(\tau)) = \tau_2$.
- $\alpha_1 = \text{read}(r, w)$, $\alpha_2 = \text{write}(w')$. Similar to the above case.
- $\alpha_1 = \text{read}(r, w)$, $\alpha_2 = \text{read}(r', w')$ and $r \in p$ $r' \in p'$, and $p \neq p' \in \mathcal{T}$. Let $\tau_1 = \alpha_1(\tau) = (E_1, \text{po}_1, \text{rf}_1, \text{HB}_1)$. Let $\tau_2 = \alpha_2(\tau)$. Since $\tau_1 \vdash_{\text{G}} \alpha_2$, we have $w' \in \text{readable}(\tau_1, r, x)$ and hence $w' \in \text{readable}(\tau, r, x)$. Hence, $\tau \vdash_{\text{G}} \alpha_2$. Let $\tau_3 = \alpha_2(\tau) = (E_3, \text{po}_3, \text{rf}_3, \text{HB}_3)$. Since $\tau \vdash_{\text{G}} \alpha_2$, we have $w \in \text{readable}(\tau, r, x)$. We need to show that $w \in \text{readable}(\tau_3, r, x)$. Assume $w \notin \text{readable}(\tau_3, r, x)$. It follows that there is a $w'' \in \text{visible}(\tau_3, r', x)$ such that $w \text{ HB}_{3p} w''$. To get $w \text{ HB}_{3p} w''$, there are two possible cases:
 1. $w \text{ HB}_p w''$. Since $w'' \in \text{visible}(\tau_3, r', x)$ it follows that $w'' \in \text{visible}(\tau, r', x)$. Since $w \text{ HB}_p w''$ and $w'' \in \text{visible}(\tau, r', x)$, it follows that $w \notin \text{readable}(\tau, r, x)$. This is a contradiction.
 2. $w' [\text{po} \cup \text{rf}]^+ w''$, $w [\text{po} \cup \text{rf}]^+ w'''$ for some $w''' \in \text{visible}(\tau, r', x)$. Since $w' [\text{po} \cup \text{rf}]^+ w''$, $w [\text{po} \cup \text{rf}]^+ w'''$ it follows that $w' [\text{po}_1 \cup \text{rf}_1]^+ w''$, $w [\text{po}_1 \cup \text{rf}_1]^+ w'''$. Since $w'' \in \text{visible}(\tau, r, x)$ we have $w'' \text{ HB}_{p'} w$ and hence we get $w' \text{ HB}_{1p'} w'''$, i.e $w' \notin \text{readable}(\tau_1, r', x)$. This is a contradiction.
Define $\tau_4 = \alpha_1(\tau_3) = (E_4, \text{po}_4, \text{rf}_4, \text{HB}_4)$. To show that $(\alpha_1 \bullet \alpha_2)(\tau) \equiv (\alpha_2 \bullet \alpha_1)(\tau)$, we need to show that if $w'' \text{ HB}_{2p} w$ then $w'' \text{ HB}_{4p} w$. If we had $w'' \text{ HB}_{2p} w$ because of $w'' [\text{po} \cup \text{rf}]^+ w$ then we have $w'' [\text{po}_4 \cup \text{rf}_4]^+ w$. Hence, we have $w'' \text{ HB}_{4p} w$. If $\neg(w'' [\text{po} \cup \text{rf}]^+ w)$, then it means that $w'' \in \text{visible}(\tau, r, x)$. Since $\tau \xrightarrow{\text{read}(r', w')} \tau_3$, will update only the $\text{HB}_{3p'}$ not HB_{3p} , we have $w'' \in \text{visible}(\tau_3, r, x)$. Hence, we have $w'' \text{ HB}_{4p} w$. A similar argument follows for other cases.

Lemma 43. *If $\tau \equiv \tau'$, $\tau \vdash_{\text{G}} \alpha_1 \bullet \alpha_2$ and $\alpha_1 \sim_{\text{spb1}} \alpha_2$ then $\tau' \vdash_{\text{G}} \alpha_2 \bullet \alpha_1$ and $(\alpha_1 \bullet \alpha_2)(\tau) \equiv (\alpha_2 \bullet \alpha_1)(\tau')$.*

Proof. Follows from Lemmas 41 and 42.

From Lemma 43 we have following lemma.

Lemma 44. *If $\tau \equiv \tau'$, $\tau \vdash_{\text{G}} \pi_1 \bullet \pi_2$ and $\pi_1 \sim_{\text{spb1}} \pi_2$ then $\tau' \vdash_{\text{G}} \pi_2 \bullet \pi_1$ and $(\pi_1 \bullet \pi_2)(\tau) \equiv (\pi_2 \bullet \pi_1)(\tau')$.*

Lemma 45. *If $\tau \vDash_{\text{Gt}} \pi$, $\tau \vDash_{\text{G}} \text{write}(w)$ and $w \in p$ then $\pi = \pi \bullet \text{write}(w) \bullet \pi''$ for some π' and π'' where π' is p-free.*

Lemma 46. *If $\tau \vdash_{\text{Gt}} \pi$, $\tau \vdash_{\text{G}} \text{read}(r, w)$ and $r \in p$ then $\pi = \pi \bullet \text{read}(r, w') \bullet \pi''$ for some π' , π'' and w' where π' is p -free.*

For a observation sequences $\pi = \alpha_1 \alpha_2 \cdots \alpha_n$ and π' we write $\pi \gg_{in} \pi'$ to represent that $\pi' = \pi_0 \bullet \alpha_1 \bullet \pi_1 \bullet \alpha_2 \pi_2 \cdots \alpha_n \bullet \pi_n$, i.e. π occurs as a non-contiguous sub-word in π' . If $\pi \gg_{in} \pi'$, then we define $\pi' \ominus \pi = \pi_0 \bullet \pi_1 \bullet \pi_2 \cdots \bullet \pi_n$.

Definition 12 (Pre(π, α)). *For observation sequence π and observable $\alpha = \pi[i]$, we define $\text{Pre}(\pi, \alpha)$ as the subword π' of π such that (i) $\alpha \in \pi$, (ii) $\pi[j] \in \pi'$ for some $j : 1 \leq j < i$ and there exists $k : j < k \leq i$ such that $\pi[k] \in \pi'$ and $\neg(\pi[j] \sim_{\text{spbl}} \pi[k])$*

Lemma 47. *If $\pi' = \text{Pre}(\pi, \alpha)$ and $\pi'' = \pi \ominus \pi'$ then $\pi \approx_{\text{spbl}} \pi' \bullet \pi''$.*

Lemma 48. *If $\pi \approx_{\text{spbl}} \pi' \bullet \pi''$ and $\alpha \in \pi$ then $\text{Pre}(\pi, \alpha) = \text{Pre}(\pi', \alpha)$.*

Lemma 49. *If $\tau \vdash_{\text{G}} \pi$ then there exists π' such that $\tau \vdash_{\text{Gt}} \pi \bullet \pi'$.*

Lemma 50. *If $\tau \models \text{CM}$, $\tau \vdash_{\text{G}} \pi \bullet \alpha$, where $\alpha = \text{read}(r, w^*)$ is a observable corresponding to a read event from process p , and π is p -free then there exists write event $w \in \mathcal{W}$ (can be initialization) such that $\tau \vdash_{\text{G}} \text{read}(r, w) \bullet \pi$.*

Proof. Let $\pi = \alpha_1 \alpha_2 \cdots \alpha_n$ and $\tau_0 \xrightarrow{\alpha_1}_{\text{tr}} \tau_1 \xrightarrow{\alpha_2}_{\text{tr}} \tau_2 \cdots \xrightarrow{\alpha_n}_{\text{tr}} \tau_n$, where $\tau_0 = \tau$. Let $\tau_i = (E_i, \text{po}_i, \text{rf}_i, \text{HB}_i)$. Define $w \in \mathcal{W}$ such that (i) $w \in \text{readable}(\tau_0, r, x)$ and (ii) there is no $w' \in \text{visible}(\tau_0, r, x)$ with $w \text{HB}_{np} w'$. Such a w exists since π is p -free, so all the observables α_i are issued in process other than that of r . Thus, when r is enabled, we can choose any latest write done earlier in τ . Each transition $\tau_{i-1} \xrightarrow{\alpha_i}_{\text{tr}} \tau_i$ will only update $\text{HB}_{i p'}$ where $p' \neq p$. We define a sequence of traces $\tau'_0, \tau'_1, \tau'_2 \cdots \tau'_n$ such that (I) $\tau_0 \xrightarrow{\text{read}(r, w)}_{\text{tr}} \tau'_0$, (II) $\tau'_i \vdash_{\text{G}} \alpha_{i+1}$, and (III) $\tau_{i+1} = \alpha_{i+1}(\tau_i)$ for all $i : 0 \leq i < n$.

Define $\text{po} = \{(e, r) \mid e \in p\}$, $\text{rf} = (w, r)$ and

$$\text{HB} = \text{HB}_p \cup \left(\bigcup_{p': p_1 - p_n, p' \neq p} \text{HB}_{p'} \right)$$

where $\text{HB}_{p'} = \text{HB}_{0p'} \cup \{(e, r) \mid (e \text{po } r)\} \cup (w, r)$ and $\text{HB}_p = [\text{HB}_{0p} \cup \text{HB}_p'']^+$ and HB_p'' is computed as follows:

- (i) Initially, $\text{HB}_p'' = \{(e'', e') \mid e'' \in \text{visible}(\tau_0, r, x)\}$.
- (ii) Then, for all events e_r , e_w and e'_w if $e_r \in p$, $e_w \text{rf } e_r$ and $e_w [\text{HB}_{0p}; \text{HB}_p'']^+ e'_w$ then $\text{HB}_p'' = \text{HB}_p'' \cup (e_r, e'_w)$.

Define $E'_i \cup r$, $\text{po}'_i = \text{po}_i \cup \text{po}$, $\text{rf}'_i = \text{rf}_i \cup \text{rf}$.

We show that the conditions (II), (III) and (IV) $\text{HB}'_i = \text{HB}_i \cup \text{HB}$ hold. We define HB'_i inductively. Define $\text{HB}'_0 = \text{HB}_0 \cup \text{HB}$ and let HB'_i be the HB relation of $\alpha_i(\tau'_i = (\ell(\mathcal{W}'_{i-1}) \cup \ell(\mathcal{R}'_{i-1}), \text{po}'_{i-1}, \text{rf}'_{i-1}, \text{HB}'_{i-1}'))$ for all $i : 1 \leq i < n$. The base case holds trivially.

Inductive step: Case $\alpha_{i+1} = \text{write}(w')$ is trivial. Suppose $\alpha_{i+1} = \text{read}(r', w')$, $r' \in p'$. If $w' \in \tau$, then the proof is trivial. Assume otherwise. Suppose for the contradiction that $w' \notin \text{readable}(\tau'_i, r', x)$. Since $w' \notin \text{readable}(\tau'_i, r', x)$ and $w' \in \text{readable}(\tau_i, r', x)$, it follows that there is event $w'' \in \text{visible}(\tau_i, r', x)$ such that $w' \text{ HB } w''$. We got $w' \text{ HB } w''$ because either $w' [po \cup rf]^+ w''$ or $w' \text{ HB}_{p'} w''$. If we consider the case $w' [po \cup rf]^+ w''$, then $w' \notin \text{visible}(\tau_i, r', x)$, which is a contradiction. Consider the case $w' \text{ HB}_{p'} w''$. Since $\text{HB}_{p'} = \text{HB}_{0p'} \cup \{(e, r) \mid (e \text{ po } r)\} \cup (w, r)$ and r has no successor in $[po_j \cup rf_j]^+$ for all $j : 1 \leq j < i$, we have $p = p'$. This is a contradiction.

Since $\tau_0 \xrightarrow{\text{read}(r, w)}_{\text{tr}} \tau'_0$ modifies **HB** relation only for the process p and π is p -free, $\text{HB}_i' = \text{HB}_i \cup \text{HB}$ holds. Therefore, (II), (III) and (IV) $\text{HB}_i' = \text{HB}_i \cup \text{HB}$ hold.

Definition 13 (Linearization of trace extension). For a trace extension τ and a sequence of observations π , we define π as the linearization of τ if (i) π contains the same events as τ and (ii) events in π are ordered following the relation $(\text{po} \cup \text{rf})$.

Definition 14 (Trace extension τ generates π). For the trace extension τ and an observation sequence π , we define that DPOR Algorithm generates π (or simply τ generates π) if some

Lemma 51. If $\tau \vdash_{\text{gt}} \pi$ then τ will generate π' for some $\pi' \approx_{\text{spbl}} \pi$

Proof. We use induction on $|\pi|$. If τ is the complete trace, then it holds trivially. Assume that $\tau \vdash_{\text{gt}} \pi$. Consider that τ generates α . α can be either a write event or a read event.

(i) Assume that τ generates $\text{write}(w)$. It follows that $\tau \vdash_{\text{G}} \text{write}(w)$. By Lemma 45, we have $\pi = \pi' \bullet \pi''$ such that π' is w -free. Since π' is w -free it follows that $\pi \approx_{\text{spbl}} w \bullet \pi' \bullet \pi''$, and hence by Lemma 44, it $\tau \vdash_{\text{gt}} w \bullet \pi' \bullet \pi''$. Hence, there is a trace τ' such that $\tau \xrightarrow{\text{write}(e)}_{\text{tr}} \tau'$ and $\tau' \vdash_{\text{gt}} \pi' \bullet \pi''$. By the induction hypothesis, it follows that τ' generates $\pi''' \approx_{\text{spbl}} \pi' \bullet \pi''$. Hence, τ generates $w \bullet \pi'''$. The result follows since $\pi \approx_{\text{spbl}} w \bullet \pi'''$.

(ii) Assume that τ generates $\text{read}(r, w^*)$. It follows that $\tau \vdash_{\text{G}} \text{read}(r, w)$. By Lemma 46 we have $\pi = \pi' \bullet \text{read}(r, w) \pi''$ such that π' is r -clear. We consider the following two cases for w' .

1. $w \in \tau$. This is trivial since the DPOR algorithm will let r to branch on all the possible writes $e \in \text{readable}(\tau, r, x)$ [lines —] including w .
2. $w \in \pi'$ Let $\pi_1 = \text{Pre}(\pi', w)$. By Lemma 50 we have $\tau \vdash_{\text{G}} \text{read}(r, w') \bullet \pi'$ for some w' . By Lemma 49 we have $\tau \vdash_{\text{gt}} \text{read}(r, w') \bullet \pi' \bullet \pi_2$ for some π_2 . That is, there exists τ' such that $\tau \xrightarrow{\text{read}(r, w')} \tau'$ and $\tau' \vdash_{\text{gt}} \pi' \bullet \pi_2$. By the induction hypothesis, for trace τ' DPOR algorithm generates some π_3 such that $\pi_3 \approx_{\text{spbl}} \pi' \bullet \pi_2$. Since $\pi_1 = \text{Pre}(\pi', w)$ and $\pi_3 \approx_{\text{spbl}} \pi' \bullet \pi_2$ by applying Lemma 48 we get $\pi_1 \gg_{\text{in}} \pi_3$. Since π' is r -free, τ generates $\pi_1 \bullet \text{read}(r, w)$. Let $\pi_4 \approx_{\text{spbl}} \pi \ominus (\pi_1 \bullet \text{read}(r, w))$. By applying lemma 47 we

get $\pi \approx_{\text{spb1}} \pi_1 \bullet \text{read}(r, w) \bullet \pi_4$. Let $\tau' = (\pi_1 \bullet \text{read}(r, w))(\tau)$. By applying lemma 44 we get $\tau \vdash_{\text{Gt}} \pi_1 \bullet \text{read}(r, w) \bullet \pi_4$. Let $\tau' = (\pi_1 \bullet \text{read}(r, w))(\tau)$, i.e. $\tau' \vdash_{\text{Gt}} \pi_4$. By applying the induction hypothesis, it follows that τ' generates some $\pi_5 \approx_{\text{spb1}} \pi_4$. In other words τ generates $\pi_1 \bullet \text{read}(r, w) \bullet \pi_5$ where $\pi \approx_{\text{spb1}} \pi_1 \bullet \text{read}(r, w) \bullet \pi_5$.

G Experiments Details

For each example, we have three versions by parameterizing the number of processes and instructions. In version 1, we have four processes per program and three to five instructions per process. Version 2 is obtained allowing each process to have seven-ten instructions. Version 3 expands version 2 by allowing each program to have up to five-six processes and up to 15-20 instructions. The number of instructions is increased by introducing fresh variables and having reads/writes on them. Versions 2,3 serve as a stress test for CONSCHECKER as increasing the number of instructions and processes increases the number of consistent traces. CONSCHECKER took $< 3s$ to finish running all version 1 programs, about 30s to finish running all version 2 programs and about 200s to finish running all version 3 programs.

Table 5. Evaluating behaviour of CONSCHECKER on classical benchmarks

Program	CCv	CC	CM
Causality Violation [12]	UNSAFE	UNSAFE	UNSAFE
Causal Violation [13]	SAFE	SAFE	SAFE
Co-Read Atomicity	UNSAFE	UNSAFE	UNSAFE
Delivery Order [11]	UNSAFE	UNSAFE	SAFE
Long Fork [12]	UNSAFE	UNSAFE	UNSAFE
Lost Update [12]	UNSAFE	UNSAFE	UNSAFE
Lost Update-2 [12]	UNSAFE	UNSAFE	UNSAFE
Modification Order	UNSAFE	UNSAFE	UNSAFE
Message Passing [10]	SAFE	SAFE	SAFE
Conflict violation [13]	UNSAFE	UNSAFE	UNSAFE
Serializability violation [13]	UNSAFE	UNSAFE	UNSAFE
Read Atomicity [13]	UNSAFE	UNSAFE	UNSAFE
Read Committed [13]	UNSAFE	UNSAFE	UNSAFE
Repeated Read [13]	UNSAFE	UNSAFE	UNSAFE
Repeated Read-2 [13]	UNSAFE	UNSAFE	UNSAFE
Load Buffer	SAFE	SAFE	SAFE
Store Buffer	UNSAFE	UNSAFE	UNSAFE
Write-po-Read	UNSAFE	UNSAFE	UNSAFE
Write-po-Read-2	UNSAFE	UNSAFE	UNSAFE
Write Skew [12]	UNSAFE	UNSAFE	UNSAFE

Table 6. Detailed version of Table 5; CONSCHECKER on the classical benchmarks under CCv semantics.

Program	Outcome	Execution Time		
		Version(i)	Version(ii)	Version(iii)
Causality Violation	UNSAFE	0.04s	0.06s	1.63s
Causal Violation	SAFE	0.04s	0.10s	8s
Co-Read Atomicity	UNSAFE	0.04s	0.05s	0.64s
Delivery Order	UNSAFE	0.04s	0.06s	0.50s
Load Buffer	SAFE	0.04s	1.2s	1.5s
Long Fork	UNSAFE	0.05s	0.36s	7s
Lost Update	UNSAFE	0.04s	0.06s	0.06s
Lost Update-2	UNSAFE	0.04s	0.06s	0.07s
Modification Order	UNSAFE	0.05s	0.06s	0.14s
Message Passing	SAFE	0.05s	0.12s	4s
Conflict Violation	UNSAFE	0.05s	0.22s	0.70s
Serializability Violation	UNSAFE	0.08s	0.11s	5s
Read Atomicity	UNSAFE	0.05s	0.44s	10s
Read Committed	UNSAFE	0.05s	0.06s	0.14s
Repeated Read	UNSAFE	0.05s	0.06s	1s
Repeated Read-2	UNSAFE	0.05s	0.06s	0.18s
Store Buffer	UNSAFE	0.04s	0.06s	9s
Write-po-Read	UNSAFE	0.05s	0.07s	3s
Write-po-Read-2	UNSAFE	0.05s	0.07s	23s
Write Skew	UNSAFE	0.04s	0.06s	6s

Table 7. Detailed version of Table 5; CONSCHECKER on the classical benchmarks under CC semantics.

Program	Outcome	Execution Time		
		Version(i)	Version(ii)	Version(iii)
Causality Violation	UNSAFE	0.04s	0.08s	2s
Causal Violation	SAFE	0.04s	0.20s	20s
Co-Read Atomicity	UNSAFE	0.04s	0.10s	0.7s
Delivery Order	UNSAFE	0.04s	0.07s	0.40s
Load Buffer	SAFE	0.04s	1.5s	1.5s
Long Fork	UNSAFE	0.05s	0.40s	7s
Lost Update	UNSAFE	0.04s	0.06s	0.07s
Lost Update-2	UNSAFE	0.04s	0.06s	0.07s
Modification Order	UNSAFE	0.05s	0.08s	0.20s
Message Passing	SAFE	0.05s	0.12s	3.7s
Conflict Violation	UNSAFE	0.05s	0.40s	0.72s
Serializability Violation	UNSAFE	0.05s	10s	6s
Read Atomicity	UNSAFE	0.05s	0.5s	12s
Read Committed	UNSAFE	0.05s	0.10s	0.3s
Repeated Read	UNSAFE	0.05s	0.1s	1.7s
Repeated Read-2	UNSAFE	0.05s	0.1s	0.7s
Store Buffer	UNSAFE	0.04s	0.12s	9s
Write-po-Read	UNSAFE	0.05s	0.07s	6s
Write-po-Read-2	UNSAFE	0.05s	0.07s	35s
Write Skew	UNSAFE	0.04s	0.07s	9s

Table 8. Detailed version of Table 5; CONSCHECKER on the classical benchmarks under CM semantics.

Program	Outcome	Execution Time		
		Version(i)	Version(ii)	Version(iii)
Causality Violation	UNSAFE	0.04s	0.08s	4.6s
Causal Violation	SAFE	0.04s	0.20s	36s
Co-Read Atomicity	UNSAFE	0.04s	0.10s	2.30s
Delivery Order	SAFE	0.04s	0.3s	8.5s
Load Buffer	SAFE	0.04s	2.7s	3.5s
Long Fork	UNSAFE	0.05s	0.8s	16s
Lost Update	UNSAFE	0.04s	0.06s	0.07s
Lost Update-2	UNSAFE	0.04s	0.06s	0.07s
Modification Order	UNSAFE	0.05s	0.08s	0.25s
Message Passing	SAFE	0.05s	0.12s	9s
Conflict Violation	UNSAFE	0.05s	0.40s	0.72s
Serializability Violation	UNSAFE	0.05s	23s	13s
Read Atomicity	UNSAFE	0.05s	0.8s	24s
Read Committed	UNSAFE	0.05s	0.10s	0.3s
Repeated Read	UNSAFE	0.05s	0.1s	2s
Repeated Read-2	UNSAFE	0.05s	0.1s	0.5s
Store Buffer	UNSAFE	0.04s	0.12s	15s
Write-po-Read	UNSAFE	0.05s	0.07s	5s
Write-po-Read-2	UNSAFE	0.05s	0.07s	33s
Write Skew	UNSAFE	0.04s	0.07s	16s